

The Role of Spaces for Balancing SDG's Goals by 2030

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Abstract:- The SDG's goals are served as the data upper, which Carbon Emission Reduction. By some countries which are signed international agreement in Paris, they promising to push the percentage of carbon emission in their country. For Indonesia government announced that could be attained at 26 %.

From the tables, we can conclude than the carbon emission reduction are fluctuated. With the range from -195, 72% in 2015 at the bottom and 137, 41% at the top in 2012. The most increasing percentage contributed in 2012 with 110%, while at the other side the sharply decreasing happened at 2015 by 55%.

The sources of carbon emission is divided by energy; industry, agriculture; waste, and forest. (Ministry of Forest, 2021).

The minimum of percentages of green open spaces is 20% in every sites while 10% is the minimum percentages of grey open spaces. (Law 2007 about Spatial Planning).

The period of observation are during 2010 – 2020, considering the data availability. The scope of research is 34 provinces in Indonesia. We are already collected data for several variables which are predicted to be the causes of carbon emission. As follows : The percentage of national carbon emission nationally; The household consumption; The government spending; The human development index; The value of export; The value of import; The total population; The percentage of inflation; The number of electricity tower; and The number of electricity network.

Consist of the step of analysis, the standar of taking the results : The Step of research consist of : grouping the data gathered from National Statistical Board from different file into one file each variable; Clustering the region by my previous research related to existence of city flagship area to enlarge the management as greater area; Combine each variables into one sheet become 1 file; Making identification by setted that according the predicted columns based on the level of impact to carbon emission reduction reduction; High list every cell by certain coloured in order to make sure the differentiation by these three groups : below mean, mean, upper mean; The last step is give scores each each cell with this rule : 1 for below mean; 2 for mean; and 3

for upper mean, and make results regarding the analysis before.

There are 6 cluster of region (sub island / islands) categorized as developed areas, while the other 7 classified as developing areas, and none of them is poverty areas.

They are : Developed Areas (inflation minimum once in 10 years more than 10%): cluster 1 (Aceh – Sumatera Utara); cluster 2 (Sumatera Barat - Riau – Kepulauan Riau); cluster 3 (Jambi – Sumatera Selatan – Bengkulu – Kepulauan Bangka Belitung); cluster 4 (Lampung – Banten); cluster 7 (Jawa Timur – Bali – Nusa Tenggara Barat – Nusa Tenggara Timur); dan cluster 10 (Kalimantan Selatan – Kalimantan Timur- Kalimantan Utara); Developing Areas (inflation minimum once in 10 years less than 10%): : Cluster 5 (DKI Jarta – Jawa Barat); cluster 6 (Jawa Tengah – DIY); cluster 8-9 (Kalimantan Barat – Kalimantan Tengah); cluster 11 (Sulawesi Utara- Gorontalo- Sulawesi Tenggara); cluster 12 (Sulawesi Tengah – Sulawesi Selatan – Sulawesi Barat); dan cluster 13 (Maluku- Maluku Utara-Papua Barat-Papua); Poverty areas (inflation minimum once in 10 years more than 5%): none of 13 clusters.

The attainment of carbon emission targets during 2010-2020 are assumed impacted of the spaces both public and private : Carbon emission : <0%, 0.01-100%, and > 100.01%; Household Consumption : 100.000.000-300.000.000; Government Spending : 188.000.000-44.000.000; IPM : 66% - 72%; Export : 4.000-6.000; Import : 4.000-6.000; Penduduk : >7.000.000; Inflation : <0, >5, >10; Towers : 1.000-2.000; Networks : 4.500 – 7.250.

The enlargement and reducing stock of spaces are proposed by the achievement of green shading (upper mean) or yellow shading (below in between bottom and too mean) and pink shading (below mean). Level of wealth in **green zone** at Sumatera Utara, Banten, DKI Jakarta, Jawa Tengah, Jawa Timur; **yellow zone** at Aceh, Sumatera Barat, Riau, Kepulauan Riau, Sumatera Selatan, Lampung, Jawa Barat, Bali, Kalimantan Barat, Kalimantan Timur; and **pink zone** at Jambi, Bengkulu, Kepulauan Bangka Belitung, DIY, Nusa Tenggara Barat, Nusa Tenggara Timur, Kalimantan Tengah, Kalimantan Selatan, Kalimantan Utara, Sulawesi Utara, Gorontalo, Sulawesi Tenggara, Sulawesi Tengah,

Sulawesi Selatan, Sulawesi Barat, Maluku, Maluku Utara, Papua Barat, dan Papua. Government Spending in **green zone** in Sumatera Utara, DKI Jakarta, Jawa Barat, Jawa Tengah, Jawa Timur, Sulawesi Selatan, Maluku Utara, dan Papua ; **yellow zones** in Aceh, Sumatera Barat, Riau, Sumatera Selatan, Lampung, DIY, Bali , Nusa Tenggara Timur, Nusa Tenggara Barat, Kalimantan Barat, Kalimantan Tengah, Kalimantan Selatan, Kalimantan Timur, Sulawesi Utara, Sulawesi Tenggara, Sulawesi Tengah and **pink zones** Kepulauan Riau, Jambi, Bengkulu, Kepulauan Bangka Belitung, Banten, Kalimantan Utara, Gorontalo, Sulawesi Barat, Maluku, Papua Barat,;

The linkage between each variables as so the row of columns can be grouped as new policies for each provinces. For Green zone : reduce the housing estates, education spaces, industrial and trade centres, and office complex, enlarge the spaces for recreational, forest and wet lands, public infrastructures, green public free and rent areas; and grey private open spaces; For Yellow zone : maintain all area dan keep existance of the all function spaces; For the pink zone : reverse back from the point a.

I. INTRODUCTION

➤ Background

Table 1 The Percentages of Carbon Emission Reduction Targets Achievement

	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
BAU (Juta ton CO ₂ e)	1.334,00	1.519,85	1.569,38	1.611,30	1.671,00	1.702,37	1.768,91	1.820,49	1.862,96	1.911,40
ER CM1 (Juta ton CO ₂ e)	1.334,00	1.332,00	1.333,00	1.338,00	1.347,00	1.359,00	1.375,00	1.394,00	1.418,00	1.445,58
Target ER CM1 (Juta ton CO ₂ e)		187,85	236,38	273,30	324,00	343,37	393,91	426,49	444,96	465,82
Inventory (Juta ton CO ₂ e)	809,98	1.054,08	1.244,58	1.331,41	1.508,97	2.374,40	1.335,52	1.353,85	1.615,57	1.866,55
Persentase Target ER terhadap CM1		247%	137,41%	102,41%	50,01%	-195,72%	110,02%	109,41%	55,60%	9,63%

Source: Ministry of Environment and Forestry, 2021

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From the tables, we can conclude than the carbon emission reduction are fluctuated. With the range from -195, 72 % in 2015 at the bottom and 137, 41 % at the top in 2012. The most increasing percentage contributed in 2012 with 110 %, while at the other side the sharply decreasing happener at 2015 by 55 %.

Because the fluctuation of those condition may be reoccurred, we try to find which factors affecting this situation.

II. LITERATURES

The sources of carbon emission is divided by energy; industry, agriculture; waste, and forest.(Ministry of Forest, 2021).

The minimum of percentages of green open spaces is 20 % in every sites while 10 % is the minimum percentages of grey open spaces. (Law 2007 about Spatial Planning).

Compact cities (ITB,2021)

Every part of Indonesia can not divided from the characteristic of urban and rural, but a holistic univication by the share of funding and management to optimize the wealth, reduce subsidies, and reach the SDG’s goals.

A. Data and Hypothesis

➤ Data

The period of observation are during 2010 – 2020, considering the datas availability.

The scope of research is 34 provinces in Indonesia.

We are already collected data for several variables which are predicted to be the causes of carbon emission. As follows :

- The percentage of national carbon emission nationally;
- The household consumption;
- The government spending;
- The human development index;
- The value of export;
- The value of import;
- The total population;
- The presentage of inflation;
- The number of electricity tower;
- The number of electricity network.

➤ *Hypothesis*

Hypotehesis are can be explained as follows :

- The percentage of national carbon emission nationally are affected by these variables : The household consumption; The government spending; The human development index; The value of export;The value of import;The total population;The presentage of inflation;The number of electricity tower;The number of electricity network.
- The amount of those variables can be grouped by the means of each variables by divided the amount of Indonesia and the number of provinces.
- The proxys of those variables can explained as these : CARBON EMISSION with **ENVIRONMENT SUSTAINABILITY (THE NEED OF FOREST AND WET LANDS)**; HOUSEHOLD COMSUPTION with **LEVEL OF WEALTH** (the need of space of recreations and public free open spaces); GOVERNMENT SPENDING with **GOVERNMENT SUBSIDIZES** (The Need of public infrastructures spaces); like roads, lakes,rivers,ports, an airports; **IPM** with EDUCATION SPACES (kindergartens, schools, and university; **EKSPOR** with INDUSTRIAL ESTATES; **IMPOR** with TRADE CENTRES; **PENDUDUK** with HOUSING ESTATES; **INFLATION** with OFFICE BUILDINGS; **TOWERS**

with GREEN PUBLIC OPEN SPACES; GREY PRIVAT OPEN SPACES with NETWORKS.

- So, those proxys of each variables as description of the needs and availability of spaces.

III. METHODOLOGY

➤ *Methodology Consist of the step of Analysis, the Standar of taking the Results.*

- The Step of research consist of : grouping the datas gathered from National Stathistical Board from difeerent file into one file each variable;
- Clustering the region by my previous research related to existance of city flagship area to enlarge the management as greater area;
- Combine each variables into one sheet become 1 file;
- Making identification by setted that according the predicted columns based on the level of impact to carbon emission reduction reduction;
- Highlist every cell by certain coloured in order to make sure the differentiaton by these three groups : below mean, mean, upper mean;
- The last step is give scores each each cell with this rule : 1 for below mean; 2 for mean; and 3 for upper mean, and make results regarding the analysis before.

IV. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Table 2 Dataset of Variables that Predicted have Correlation with Carbon Emission Reduction Targets

KODE SUB PULAU / KEPULAUAN	NAMA PROVINSI	TAHUN	CARBON EMISSION	HOUSE HOLD CONSUPTION	GOVERNMENT SPENDING	IPM	EKSPORT	IMPOR	POPULATION	INFLATION	TOWERS	NETWORKS
1	ACEH	2010	0	55438432 .71	19572175 .74	67.09	1 326,3	223,6	4494410	4.64	159.26	1579.77
1	ACEH	2011	247	59464214 .13	22804177 .33	67.45	1 406,3	345,7	4494410	3.32	159.26	1579.77
1	ACEH	2012	137,41	63571782 .01	25153975 .63	67.81	1 197,2	546,1	4494410	0.06	156.93	1755.06
1	ACEH	2013	102,41	68817214 .34	29655933 .43	68.30	9 30,4	483,5	4494410	6.39	128.54	1815.04
1	ACEH	2014	50,01	74185221 .08	31463525 .27	68.81	5 01,2	459,2	4494410	7.83	201.25	1965.55
1	ACEH	2015	- 195,72	79851130 .37	35180034 .54	69.45	3 8,8	1213, 1	4494410	1.27	232.10	2119.00
1	ACEH	2016	110,02	85639166 .37	31802695 .62	70.00	0 ,0	1059, 2	4494410	3.13	232.10	2119.00
1	ACEH	2017	109,41	91768957 .81	34058018 .76	70.60	0 ,0	1106, 4	4494410	4.86	224.27	2409.11
1	ACEH	2018	55,6	97053993 .71	35423023 .59	71.19	0 ,8	1656, 7	4494410	1.93	221.13	2587.71
1	ACEH	2019	9,63	10329449 6.91	38121413 .50	71.90	4 ,8	1593, 1	4494410	1.93	239.55	2781.50
1	ACEH	2020	0	10442846 8.72	35299828 .62	71.99	0 ,3	1569, 7	4494410	1.93	239.55	2781.50
1	SUMATERA UTAR	2010	0	17833231 2.83	25707619 .69	67.09	7 429,0	3296, 3	1298220 4	7.65	2450.67	7194.03

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1	SUMATERA UTARA	2011	247	19815143 5.05	29568520 .01	67. 34	1 0 057,7	4606, 5	1298220 4	3.54	2450. 67	7194.03
1	SUMATERA UTARA	2012	137,41	22274492 2.75	33386620 .71	67. 74	8 871,9	4775, 6	1298220 4	3.79	3501. 67	7809.32
1	SUMATERA UTARA	2013	102,41	25141564 2.84	37523215 .11	68. 36	7 982,3	4826, 3	1298220 4	10.09	3625. 32	7917.24
1	SUMATERA UTARA	2014	50,01	28143138 4.00	40798560 .90	68. 87	7 808,1	4777, 7	1298220 4	8.24	4116. 45	8271.01
1	SUMATERA UTARA	2015	- 195,72	30607185 8.51	43960453 .55	69. 51	6 618,1	3771, 1	1298220 4	3.32	4241. 54	8703.67
1	SUMATERA UTARA	2016	110,02	33351172 5.39	46072715 .84	70. 00	6 768,8	3669, 9	1298220 4	6.60	4241. 54	8703.67
1	SUMATERA UTARA	2017	109,41	36405739 1.98	51838128 .31	70. 57	8 111,6	4392, 7	1298220 4	3.18	4832. 95	9671.48
1	SUMATERA UTARA	2018	55,6	39742280 9.82	56298765 .87	71. 18	7 743,3	5206, 3	1298220 4	1.00	5017. 05	10445.0 2
1	SUMATERA UTARA	2019	9,63	43076635 5.21	57417178 .40	71. 74	6 786,8	4256, 6	1298220 4	1.00	5679. 04	8324.86
1	SUMATERA UTARA	2020	0	42449498 7.37	56258272 .38	71. 77	6 921,4	3786, 1	1298220 4	1.00	5679. 04	8324.86
2	SUMATERA BARAT	2010	0	59421725 .64	14298111 .53	67. 25	2 214,6	223,6	4846909	7.84	33.45	2403.10
2	SUMATERA BARAT	2011	247	65668166 .97	15856436 .96	67. 81	3 030,0	345,7	4846909	5.37	33.45	2403.10
2	SUMATERA BARAT	2012	137,41	72191823 .49	17675534 .77	68. 36	2 362,9	546,1	4846909	4.16	32.93	2649.08
2	SUMATERA BARAT	2013	102,41	80265541 .43	19683675 .57	68. 91	2 208,6	483,5	4846909	10.87	32.91	2712.85
2	SUMATERA BARAT	2014	50,01	88282601 .42	21622467 .67	69. 36	2 105,4	459,2	4846909	11.90	72.67	3005.26

2	SUMATERA BARAT	2015	- 195,72	96531830 .74	24255718 .84	69. 98	1 753,1	1213, 1	4846909	0.85	305.1 5	3063.28
2	SUMATERA BARAT	2016	110,02	10384496 6.07	25511598 .02	70. 73	1 708,1	1059, 2	4846909	5.02	305.1 5	3063.28
2	SUMATERA BARAT	2017	109,41	11270603 4.50	26894124 .14	71. 24	2 045,5	1106, 4	4846909	2.11	283.0 3	3415.29
2	SUMATERA BARAT	2018	55,6	12263194 8.77	28994008 .80	71. 73	1 598,1	1656, 7	4846909	2.55	59.84	3496.18
2	SUMATERA BARAT	2019	9,63	13381732 5.72	31103493 .49	72. 39	1 337,7	1593, 1	4846909	2.55	821.6 8	3445.08
2	SUMATERA BARAT	2020	0	13088639 9.01	28852523 .81	72. 38	1 531,3	1569, 7	4846909	2.55	821.6 8	3445.08
2	RIAU	2010	0	10702404 5.49	15917523 .93	68. 65	1 855,0	504,7	5538367	7.00	111.2 3	2361.15
2	RIAU	2011	247	12852381 4.32	18344814 .53	68. 90	6 594,6	1175, 2	5538367	5.09	111.2 3	2361.15
2	RIAU	2012	137,41	14900145 8.78	19750383 .10	69. 15	5 552,0	1084, 9	5538367	3.35	157.6 7	2723.81
2	RIAU	2013	102,41	17147339 4.95	21227801 .18	69. 91	4 197,8	1064, 5	5538367	8.83	175.4 8	3597.44
2	RIAU	2014	50,01	19716281 5.61	20562897 .64	70. 33	4 021,3	778,1	5538367	8.53	172.6 2	3338.33
2	RIAU	2015	- 195,72	22217309 5.96	23462836 .56	70. 84	1 416,4	492,5	5538367	2.71	173.8 0	3586.45
2	RIAU	2016	110,02	24126448 1.36	25547536 .97	71. 20	0 894,4	332,7	5538367	4.19	173.8 0	3586.45
2	RIAU	2017	109,41	25900230 4.12	26760715 .29	71. 79	2 979,7	391,2	5538367	4.07	353.7 6	4069.93
2	RIAU	2018	55,6	27294074 1.94	27733833 .57	72. 44	2 506,6	436,9	5538367	2.54	317.0 9	4377.21
2	RIAU	2019	9,63	28737538 9.50	31529677 .36	73. 00	8 961,7	502,4	5538367	2.54	373.2 2	4646.79
2	RIAU	2020	0	28857667 1.18	32802658 .50	72. 71	0 403,9	310,1	5538367	2.54	373.2 2	4646.79
2	KEP. RIAU	2010	0	41227435 .61	6740477. 81	71. 13	8 328,1	118,2	1679163	6.17	301.4 7	2010.30
2	KEP. RIAU	2011	247	45818761 .02	7599014. 19	71. 61	1 1	1728, 4	1679163	3.32	301.4 7	2010.30

							346,3					
2	KEP. RIAU	2012	137,41	50422624 .19	8661512. 44	72. 36	0 462,8	1 2730, 5	1679163	3.92	371.4 3	2190.04
2	KEP. RIAU	2013	102,41	56772721 .87	9780476. 89	73. 02	1 618,7	1 2417, 3	1679163	10.09	381.2 1	2421.92
2	KEP. RIAU	2014	50,01	63725521 .84	10962687 .42	73. 40	9 116,8	2296, 2	1679163	7.49	736.4 8	2618.48
2	KEP. RIAU	2015	- 195,72	73064167 .14	12384396 .32	73. 75	7 549,8	6065, 7	1679163	2.46	736.8 0	2694.79
2	KEP. RIAU	2016	110,02	82862014 .41	13810271 .14	73. 99	7 411,7	5295, 9	1679163	3.06	736.8 0	2694.79
2	KEP. RIAU	2017	109,41	92444110 .41	14737145 .11	74. 45	7 232,2	5531, 9	1679163	3.37	882.5 4	2823.17
2	KEP. RIAU	2018	55,6	99260506 .76	14732688 .97	74. 84	7 883,9	8283, 3	1679163	2.36	969.6 2	2990.44
2	KEP. RIAU	2019	9,63	10692843 1.18	15130646 .71	75. 48	8 323,7	7965, 5	1679163	2.36	1005. 94	3346.31
2	KEP. RIAU	2020	0	10903471 7.89	14952633 .06	75. 59	9 481,8	7848, 5	1679163	2.36	1005. 94	3346.31
3	JAMBI	2010	0	44927946 .05	8024190. 02	65. 39	4 184,6	223,6	3092265	10.52	12.82	1054.17
3	JAMBI	2011	247	48838206 .95	9417666. 96	66. 14	5 348,9	345,7	3092265	2.76	12.82	1054.17
3	JAMBI	2012	137,41	54317104 .07	10881354 .28	66. 94	5 130,6	546,1	3092265	4.22	51.38	860.39
3	JAMBI	2013	102,41	59598782 .59	12000226 .23	67. 76	4 646,9	483,5	3092265	8.74	50.06	955.66
3	JAMBI	2014	50,01	66802356 .10	13000173 .13	68. 24	5 075,4	459,2	3092265	8.72	51.54	1037.45
3	JAMBI	2015	- 195,72	71817541 .17	14353139 .19	68. 89	4 086,9	1213, 1	3092265	1.37	60.37	1083.79
3	JAMBI	2016	110,02	76982264 .56	14663951 .76	69. 62	3 683,2	1059, 2	3092265	4.54	60.37	1083.79
3	JAMBI	2017	109,41	83274310 .36	15936632 .29	69. 99	4 650,0	1106, 4	3092265	2.68	50.57	1176.09
3	JAMBI	2018	55,6	89324493 .96	16968265 .43	70. 65	5 033,7	1656, 7	3092265	3.02	43.13	1219.01
3	JAMBI	2019	9,63	96343529 .88	18189861 .51	71. 26	4 331,0	1593, 1	3092265	3.02	52.77	1932.00
3	JAMBI	2020	0	97657350 .81	17840939 .69	71. 29	3 533,6	1569, 7	3092265	3.02	52.77	1932.00
3	SUMA TERA SELA TAN	2010	0	12489581 7.95	15769668 .87	64. 44	3 513,6	359,3	7450394	6.02	2380. 92	2978.86
3	SUMA TERA SELA TAN	2011	247	14535083 8.51	18500923 .96	65. 12	5057, 4	552,2	7450394	3.78	2380. 92	2978.86
3	SUMA TERA SELA TAN	2012	137,41	16401685 2.81	20445006 .34	65. 79	4 371,7	506,4	7450394	2.72	2540. 13	3863.12
3	SUMA TERA SELA TAN	2013	102,41	18828944 4.92	22542613 .64	66. 16	3 915,6	551,3	7450394	7.04	2663. 26	4162.09
3	SUMA	2014	50,01	20820839	24444772	66.	3	740	7450394	8.38	3018.	4477.49

	TERA SELA TAN			3.62	.49	75	083,8				06	
3	SUMA TERA SELA TAN	2015	- 195,72	22248765 9.92	25889700 .37	67. 46	2 442,4	1435, 5	7450394	3.05	3146. 21	4783.02
3	SUMA TERA SELA TAN	2016	110,02	24097733 8.86	26313943 .52	68. 24	1 978,6	977,7	7450394	3.68	3146. 21	4783.02
3	SUMA TERA SELA TAN	2017	109,41	25727712 1.62	29902575 .60	68. 86	3 307,4	398,7	7450394	2.85	4494. 22	5239.35
3	SUMA TERA SELA TAN	2018	55,6	27777106 2.14	32460274 .02	69. 39	3 734,1	718,7	7450394	2.78	4458. 37	5501.26
3	SUMA TERA SELA TAN	2019	9,63	29690497 5.01	36686874 .55	70. 02	3 611,9	503,3	7450394	2.78	4348. 66	5258.23
3	SUMA TERA SELA TAN	2020	0	29655535 1.56	32465000 .46	70. 01	3 050,2	936,9	7450394	2.78	4348. 66	5258.23
3	BENG KULU	2010	0	17930119 .30	5681452. 76	65. 35	4 184,6	223,6	1715518	9.08	23.24	493.95
3	BENG KULU	2011	247	20297687 .14	6214001. 11	65. 96	5 348,9	345,7	1715518	3.96	23.24	493.95
3	BENG KULU	2012	137,41	23006942 .59	6867336. 72	66. 61	5 130,6	546,1	1715518	4.61	24.04	566.95
3	BENG KULU	2013	102,41	26025111 .97	7615202. 55	67. 50	4 646,9	483,5	1715518	9.94	24.04	641.52
3	BENG KULU	2014	50,01	29476477 .89	8850671. 55	68. 06	5 075,4	459,2	1715518	10.85	43.54	729.64
3	BENG KULU	2015	- 195,72	33165076 .29	10231616 .83	68. 59	4 086,9	1213, 1	1715518	3.25	25.89	785.43
3	BENG KULU	2016	110,02	36475574 .53	11235134 .10	69. 33	3 683,2	1059, 2	1715518	5.00	25.89	785.43
3	BENG KULU	2017	109,41	39301815 .64	12028795 .14	69. 95	4 650,0	1106, 4	1715518	3.56	47.20	852.84
3	BENG KULU	2018	55,6	42192931 .74	13051200 .00	70. 64	5 033,7	1656, 7	1715518	2.35	51.06	907.45
3	BENG KULU	2019	9,63	45570351 .31	13880337 .00	71. 21	4 331,0	1593, 1	1715518	2.35	66.61	955.47
3	BENG KULU	2020	0	46324562 .29	14261866 .07	71. 40	3 533,6	1569, 7	1715518	2.35	66.61	955.47
3	KEP. BANG KA BELIT UNG	2010	0	17984595 .16	3480126. 96	66. 02	4 184,6	223,6	1223296	9.36	91.78	535.61
3	KEP. BANG KA BELIT UNG	2011	247	20157179 .83	4035831. 92	66. 59	5 348,9	345,7	1223296	5.00	91.78	535.61
3	KEP.	2012	137,41	22650828	4592183.	67.	5	546,1	1223296	6.57	111.4	664.72

	BANG KA BELIT UNG			.98	44	21	130,6				6	
3	KEP. BANG KA BELIT UNG	2013	102,41	25833873 .89	5249823. 87	67. 92	4 646,9	483,5	1223296	8.71	106.4 6	721.24
3	KEP. BANG KA BELIT UNG	2014	50,01	29332294 .80	5768625. 90	68. 27	5 075,4	459,2	1223296	6.81	234.7 1	805.43
3	KEP. BANG KA BELIT UNG	2015	- 195,72	32577016 .35	6423805. 18	69. 05	4 086,9	1213, 1	1223296	4.66	314.5 6	861.52
3	KEP. BANG KA BELIT UNG	2016	110,02	36367008 .68	7250911. 64	69. 55	3 683,2	1059, 2	1223296	7.78	314.5 6	861.52
3	KEP. BANG KA BELIT UNG	2017	109,41	40307286 .64	7691271. 99	69. 99	4 650,0	1106, 4	1223296	2.66	265.4 0	979.19
3	KEP. BANG KA BELIT UNG	2018	55,6	44168089 .23	8065844. 82	70. 67	5 033,7	1656, 7	1223296	3.45	285.9 2	1066.35
3	KEP. BANG KA BELIT UNG	2019	9,63	48174449 .58	8702146. 57	71. 30	4 331,0	1593, 1	1223296	3.45	285.9 2	1166.93
3	KEP. BANG KA BELIT UNG	2020	0	48463619 .47	8636405. 04	71. 47	3 533,6	1569, 7	1223296	3.45	285.9 2	1166.93
4	LAMP UNG	2010	0	89663683 .33	12483702 .35	63. 71	2 467,4	866,7	7608405	9.95	4.30	2425.94
4	LAMP UNG	2011	247	10296488 8.38	14518137 .08	64. 20	3 222,6	1247, 8	7608405	4.24	4.30	2425.94
4	LAMP UNG	2012	137,41	11454399 6.76	16587050 .20	64. 87	3 698,4	1716, 2	7608405	4.30	124.7 9	2793.36
4	LAMP UNG	2013	102,41	12524218 3.96	18426476 .90	65. 73	3 892,3	1552, 9	7608405	7.56	124.7 9	3182.21
4	LAMP UNG	2014	50,01	13846498 3.37	20697888 .09	66. 42	3 856,7	1393, 1	7608405	8.36	121.2 1	3392.44
4	LAMP UNG	2015	- 195,72	15323304 5.67	23972125 .49	66. 95	2 315,9	1474	7608405	4.65	121.1 2	3571.00
4	LAMP UNG	2016	110,02	16690292 5.33	25534195 .80	67. 65	1 873,6	1535, 9	7608405	2.75	121.1 2	3571.00
4	LAMP UNG	2017	109,41	18240365 8.02	26627970 .00	68. 25	2 132,2	1489, 9	7608405	3.14	124.3 8	3998.30

4	LAMPUNG	2018	55,6	20071657 7.65	27876520 .81	69. 02	1 714,2	1365, 3	7608405	2.92	237.3 8	4257.15
4	LAMPUNG	2019	9,63	22034117 2.78	29201111 .71	69. 57	1 561,2	1087, 4	7608405	2.92	237.3 8	4686.09
4	LAMPUNG	2020	0	22090612 2.30	29387687 .52	69. 69	1 555,9	911,7	7608405	2.92	237.3 8	4686.09
4	BANTEN	2010	0	16767680 9.85	12440201 .36	67. 54	9 38,0	7603, 7	1063216 6	6.18	6773. 53	7955.54
4	BANTEN	2011	247	18117485 7.92	14690532 .87	68. 22	1 106,5	1045 4,3	1063216 6	2.78	6773. 53	7955.54
4	BANTEN	2012	137,41	20170789 1.24	16606262 .30	68. 92	7 19,9	1042 4,7	1063216 6	4.41	1132 3.54	8457.80
4	BANTEN	2013	102,41	21915946 7.84	18671954 .43	69. 47	9 28,4	1069 0,8	1063216 6	9.16	1170 3.54	9750.37
4	BANTEN	2014	50,01	23403509 0.85	19237577 .65	69. 89	8 95,8	1060 5,5	1063216 6	11.27	1287 3.34	8562.97
4	BANTEN	2015	- 195,72	25338260 8.28	21118167 .43	70. 27	5 91,2	7585, 6	1063216 6	4.67	1287 3.34	8575.10
4	BANTEN	2016	110,02	27280688 8.68	22897756 .57	70. 96	7 35,3	6555, 5	1063216 6	3.26	1287 3.34	8575.10
4	BANTEN	2017	109,41	29442389 4.26	24616488 .96	71. 42	1 098,9	8135, 2	1063216 6	5.17	7443. 90	22557.5 3
4	BANTEN	2018	55,6	32178826 0.05	27576241 .87	71. 95	1 249,5	9326	1063216 6	3.78	8052. 30	23736.3 0
4	BANTEN	2019	9,63	34822911 5.87	29744840 .99	72. 44	1 227,6	8098, 4	1063216 6	3.78	7653. 14	24646.1 1
4	BANTEN	2020	0	34566662 9.05	27343037 .41	72. 45	9 38,7	7350, 4	1063216 6	3.78	7653. 14	24646.1 1
5	DKI JAKARTA	2010	0	63774045 5.50	13694665 7.70	76. 31	39519 ,8	6771 6,9	9607787	6.21	1093. 00	35061.3 8
5	DKI JAKARTA	2011	247	71377879 8.44	15930204 6.31	76. 98	46349	8830 8,7	9607787	3.97	1093. 00	35061.3 8
5	DKI JAKARTA	2012	137,41	80984507 7.26	18325965 2.61	77. 53	48018 ,2	9640 6,5	9607787	4.52	1448. 49	38168.7 5
5	DKI JAKARTA	2013	102,41	93916069 5.69	21134478 9.27	78. 08	47288 ,6	8952 2,4	9607787	8.00	1448. 00	39937.2 8
5	DKI JAKARTA	2014	50,01	10650881 37.67	22265939 8.25	78. 39	48108	8427 9,6	9607787	8.95	1348. 00	41269.0 3
5	DKI JAKARTA	2015	- 195,72	12083475 75.84	26041664 1.32	78. 99	46355 ,3	7089 9,3	9607787	3.30	1359. 54	41328.6 0
5	DKI JAKARTA	2016	110,02	13133856 27.11	28898166 5.15	79. 60	45993 ,2	7107 0,8	9607787	2.37	1359. 54	41328.6 0
5	DKI JAKARTA	2017	109,41	14372618 14.83	30685974 9.57	80. 06	51,67 5,9	8131 0,5	9607787	3.72	6095. 82	31643.1 3
5	DKI JAKARTA	2018	55,6	15719644 54.61	35447142 1.51	80. 47	54483 ,9	9357 3,4	9607787	3.27	4183. 74	32779.1 9
5	DKI JAKARTA	2019	9,63	17191439 62.44	36097705 8.91	80. 76	54044 ,4	8807 7,8	9607787	3.27	3504. 30	34107.8 8
5	DKI JAKARTA	2020	0	17260058 34.07	41316376 7.16	80. 77	53655 ,1	7175 1,4	9607787	3.27	3504. 30	34107.8 8

	RTA											
5	JAWA BARA T	2010	0	60962657 4.67	54922081 .00	66. 15	941,5	3108, 2	4305373 2	4.53	3217. 80	34053.6 0
5	JAWA BARA T	2011	247	67115866 6.78	59786927 .33	66. 67	1012, 5	5620, 4	4305373 2	2.75	3217. 80	34053.6 0
5	JAWA BARA T	2012	137,41	73427245 3.27	68994157 .99	67. 32	674,1	6168, 2	4305373 2	4.02	4013. 05	36655.2 8
5	JAWA BARA T	2013	102,41	81256832 3.76	73717544 .96	68. 25	442,7	5897, 7	4305373 2	7.97	3998. 74	39092.5 6
5	JAWA BARA T	2014	50,01	88110939 8.50	81202692 .40	68. 80	851,8	5766, 6	4305373 2	7.76	4076. 66	43096.4 6
5	JAWA BARA T	2015	- 195,72	98376522 6.82	98292764 .94	69. 50	351	4905	4305373 2	3.93	4077. 90	44071.4 3
5	JAWA BARA T	2016	110,02	10755220 40.90	10067281 6.97	70. 05	210,4	4714, 9	4305373 2	2.93	4077. 90	44071.4 3
5	JAWA BARA T	2017	109,41	11693673 87.39	10793950 0.30	70. 69	207,1	6570, 4	4305373 2	3.46	7272. 16	50791.2 0
5	JAWA BARA T	2018	55,6	12782788 95.69	11293505 8.42	71. 30	230,7	8050, 9	4305373 2	3.76	9697. 06	52878.8 6
5	JAWA BARA T	2019	9,63	13877622 69.96	11744894 4.50	72. 03	207,7	6444, 3	4305373 2	3.76	1027 3.56	54480.2 8
5	JAWA BARA T	2020	0	13789043 84.43	11868895 7.77	72. 09	184,3	5043, 2	4305373 2	3.76	1027 3.56	54480.2 8
6	JAWA TENG AH	2010	0	38963755 0.12	49467504 .64	66. 08	3863, 2	9618, 8	3238265 7	7.11	6509. 12	15315.8 9
6	JAWA TENG AH	2011	247	42991243 9.03	55282980 .32	66. 64	4678, 3	1299 8,1	3238265 7	2.87	6509. 12	15315.8 9
6	JAWA TENG AH	2012	137,41	47488673 3.82	61581493 .37	67. 21	4637, 1	1397 2,4	3238265 7	4.85	5168. 49	16600.4 2
6	JAWA TENG AH	2013	102,41	52038030 4.38	69299782 .96	68. 02	5319, 7	1573 5,8	3238265 7	8.19	5153. 86	18205.0 8
6	JAWA TENG AH	2014	50,01	57043340 1.17	75556448 .86	68. 78	5626, 9	1576 7,9	3238265 7	8.53	5154. 85	19631.4 6
6	JAWA TENG AH	2015	- 195,72	62026401 5.08	85225912 .08	69. 49	5369, 8	1071 7	3238265 7	2.56	5155. 26	20408.1 9
6	JAWA TENG AH	2016	110,02	66098858 5.60	87589147 .24	69. 98	5384, 6	8769, 1	3238265 7	2.32	5155. 26	20408.1 9
6	JAWA TENG AH	2017	109,41	71158651 0.45	94261559 .47	70. 52	5982, 3	1045 7,3	3238265 7	3.64	7096. 65	21057.0 4
6	JAWA TENG AH	2018	55,6	76480838 0.14	98717169 .57	71. 12	6579	1426 6,8	3238265 7	2.76	7150. 68	23558.0 2

	AH											
6	JAWA TENG AH	2019	9,63	82194811 6.89	10320951 7.34	71. 73	6743, 6	1235 5,5	3238265 7	2.76	7162. 82	24750.6 2
6	JAWA TENG AH	2020	0	82209550 2.18	98359804 .69	71. 87	6455, 7	8635, 6	3238265 7	2.76	7162. 82	24750.6 2
6	DI YOGY AKAR TA	2010	0	38442940 .59	9847893. 44	75. 37	2446, 8	3108, 2	3457491	7.38	0.32	1869.77
6	DI YOGY AKAR TA	2011	247	44029582 .93	11039649 .77	75. 93	3500, 5	5620, 4	3457491	3.88	0.32	1869.77
6	DI YOGY AKAR TA	2012	137,41	49403400 .71	11982949 .65	76. 15	3954, 2	6168, 2	3457491	4.31	0.32	2043.75
6	DI YOGY AKAR TA	2013	102,41	57101887 .22	13629833 .88	76. 44	3690	5897, 7	3457491	7.32	0.32	2205.79
6	DI YOGY AKAR TA	2014	50,01	62875141 .17	15347428 .32	76. 81	5299, 8	5766, 6	3457491	6.59	0.32	2369.60
6	DI YOGY AKAR TA	2015	- 195,72	68730527 .54	17214154 .28	77. 59	4776, 6	4905	3457491	3.09	0.18	2484.16
6	DI YOGY AKAR TA	2016	110,02	74429795 .62	18321761 .49	78. 38	6005, 7	4714, 9	3457491	2.29	0.18	2484.16
6	DI YOGY AKAR TA	2017	109,41	81335809 .99	19508071 .64	78. 89	5003, 4	6570, 4	3457491	4.20	-	2724.49
6	DI YOGY AKAR TA	2018	55,6	86753196 .83	21382113 .04	79. 53	4567, 7	8050, 9	3457491	2.66	-	2856.95
6	DI YOGY AKAR TA	2019	9,63	92436088 .69	22434453 .68	79. 99	4522, 8	6444, 3	3457491	2.66	-	2856.95
6	DI YOGY AKAR TA	2020	0	92753541 .94	22889206 .61	79. 97	3095, 1	5043, 2	3457491	2.66	-	2856.95
7	JAWA TIMU R	2010	0	62963036 2.60	59765151 .65	65. 36	14209 ,8	12 475,2	3747675 7	7.33	9620. 62	24018.6 9
7	JAWA TIMU R	2011	247	70334308 3.11	70530906 .42	66. 06	16964 ,4	15 721,7	3747675 7	4.72	9620. 62	24018.6 9
7	JAWA TIMU R	2012	137,41	78159154 8.57	86194972 .19	66. 74	13557 ,2	16 430,7	3747675 7	4.39	1159 5.42	26910.1 8

7	JAWA TIMU R	2013	102,41	86691617 2.60	93232474 .47	67. 55	12761 ,5	17 463,6	3747675 7	7.52	1154 7.76	28708.1 1
7	JAWA TIMU R	2014	50,01	94934343 7.70	96944244 .35	68. 14	14528 ,7	17 449,7	3747675 7	7.90	1466 8.05	30523.9 8
7	JAWA TIMU R	2015	- 195,72	10196221 40.96	10491233 3.83	68. 95	13156 ,4	13 841,2	3747675 7	3.43	1350 4.40	30824.8 1
7	JAWA TIMU R	2016	110,02	11090141 91.23	10053691 9.26	69. 74	13994 ,1	13 593,1	3747675 7	3.22	1350 4.40	30824.8 1
7	JAWA TIMU R	2017	109,41	11939150 47.01	10944400 1.07	70. 27	15737 ,7	15 472,2	3747675 7	4.37	8199. 50	34114.1 6
7	JAWA TIMU R	2018	55,6	12983904 91.77	12099106 7.09	70. 77	16985 ,6	17 652,6	3747675 7	3.03	9396. 50	35817.9 0
7	JAWA TIMU R	2019	9,63	13966044 89.98	13100393 6.27	71. 50	16536 ,8	16 545,7	3747675 7	3.03	1107 2.58	37228.9 4
7	JAWA TIMU R	2020	0	13985167 72.62	12988686 0.99	71. 71	16618 ,7	14 546,3	3747675 7	3.03	1107 2.58	37228.9 4
7	BALI	2010	0	53059800 .33	10949789 .04	70. 10	373,4	94 9,1	3890757	8.10	3.84	3223.94
7	BALI	2011	247	59713201 .51	12772674 .64	70. 87	376,0 33	1 056,5	3890757	3.75	3.84	3223.94
7	BALI	2012	137,41	65812887 .91	14643132 .46	71. 62	347,3 67	19 1,2	3890757	4.71	453.8 7	3546.60
7	BALI	2013	102,41	69651681 .90	16611925 .76	72. 09	327,5 7	28 1,9	3890757	7.35	454.0 2	3914.32
7	BALI	2014	50,01	76468024 .97	15985791 .10	72. 48	297,2 67	30 6,0	3890757	8.03	441.8 9	4335.03
7	BALI	2015	- 195,72	85910954 .33	17750679 .10	73. 27	745,1 3	14 0,8	3890757	2.70	1017. 19	4594.18
7	BALI	2016	110,02	95497686 .01	19977806 .53	73. 65	783,8 7	17 3,1	3890757	2.94	1017. 19	4594.18
7	BALI	2017	109,41	10215293 1.82	22603583 .30	74. 30	646,2	13 6,0	3890757	3.31	911.3 9	5069.64
7	BALI	2018	55,6	11176243 9.69	24531443 .84	74. 77	457,1	31 4,1	3890757	3.40	786.8 4	5247.16
7	BALI	2019	9,63	12114003 1.51	26717603 .75	75. 38	407,0 3	26 1,1	3890757	3.40	1041. 52	5706.73
7	BALI	2020	0	11995769 3.75	28068998 .65	75. 50	327,5 7	12 3,3	3890757	3.40	1041. 52	5706.73
7	NUSA TENG GARA BARA T	2010	0	42502375 .08	9183330. 60	61. 16	1995, 5	31 8,2	4500212	11.07	146.0 0	837.17
7	NUSA TENG GARA BARA T	2011	247	47321574 .78	10399526 .98	62. 14	1136, 93	32 8,9	4500212	6.38	146.0 0	837.17
7	NUSA TENG GARA BARA	2012	137,41	52815732 .96	11160516 .74	62. 98	596,6 7	28 3,7	4500212	4.10	172.7 0	976.39

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7	NUSA TENG GARA BARA T	2013	102,41	56643475 .61	11658708 .80	63. 76	400,8 67	31 4,0	4500212	9.27	170.0 4	1133.33	
7	NUSA TENG GARA BARA T	2014	50,01	62018051 .91	15387606 .46	64. 31	307,9 7	1 158,7	4500212	7.18	445.3 9	1291.47	
7	NUSA TENG GARA BARA T	2015	- 195,72	66021500 .37	16862329 .01	65. 19	491,1 3	14 5,3	4500212	3.25	393.8 0	1402.30	
7	NUSA TENG GARA BARA T	2016	110,02	70678200 .51	17766902 .48	65. 81	525,1 7	111,6	4500212	2.47	393.8 0	1402.30	
7	NUSA TENG GARA BARA T	2017	109,41	74854229 .77	19218414 .15	66. 58	366,7	81,7	4500212	3.59	418.4 9	1677.54	
7	NUSA TENG GARA BARA T	2018	55,6	79113027 .33	19757219 .46	67. 30	157,8	16 1,3	4500212	3.15	624.9 3	1776.81	
7	NUSA TENG GARA BARA T	2019	9,63	83915658 .79	20238840 .55	68. 14	64,83	180,7	4500212	3.15	795.7 5	1950.25	
7	NUSA TENG GARA BARA T	2020	0	82051299 .10	20758268 .34	68. 25	197,0 7	193,9	4500212	3.15	795.7 5	1950.25	
7	NUSA TENG GARA TIMU R	2010	0	33894767 .77	11979590 .90	59. 21	34,1	36,4	4683827	9.97	145.7 5	486.91	
7	NUSA TENG GARA TIMU R	2011	247	38363267 .80	13934970 .82	60. 24	26,33	34,1	4683827	4.32	145.7 5	486.91	
7	NUSA TENG GARA TIMU R	2012	137,41	42639921 .72	15958534 .47	60. 81	44,06 7	61,4	4683827	5.10	158.6 9	567.32	
7	NUSA TENG GARA TIMU R	2013	102,41	47342068 .61	17083005 .23	61. 68	20,86 7	161,1	4683827	8.84	160.5 4	639.57	

7	NUSA TENG GARA TIMU R	2014	50,01	50692465 .46	19486122 .13	62. 26	21,67	63,12	4683827	8.32	272.8 0	702.26
7	NUSA TENG GARA TIMU R	2015	- 195,72	56851466 .36	22091092 .85	62. 67	515,1 3	20,7	4683827	5.07	297.2 5	749.76
7	NUSA TENG GARA TIMU R	2016	110,02	61506312 .16	23994706 .03	63. 13	558,2 7	63	4683827	2.31	297.2 5	749.76
7	NUSA TENG GARA TIMU R	2017	109,41	66707542 .95	25754331 .57	63. 73	389,3	54,2	4683827	2.05	302.6 9	855.25
7	NUSA TENG GARA TIMU R	2018	55,6	71254439 .23	29098507 .51	64. 39	167,6	171,1	4683827	3.23	331.2 1	927.41
7	NUSA TENG GARA TIMU R	2019	9,63	76891365 .23	29845270 .42	65. 23	81,03	76,1	4683827	3.23	333.4 2	999.49
7	NUSA TENG GARA TIMU R	2020	0	74626626 .07	27542846 .60	65. 19	212,8 7	58,5	4683827	3.23	333.4 2	999.49
8	KALI MANT AN BARA T	2010	0	47904067 .54	10912057 .82	61. 97	580,9	13 1,1	4395983	8.52	230.5 1	1434.72
8	KALI MANT AN BARA T	2011	247	53680214 .16	12278039 .14	62. 35	1260, 8	20 7,6	4395983	4.91	230.5 1	1434.72
8	KALI MANT AN BARA T	2012	137,41	59923683 .53	12750236 .72	63. 41	964,1	47 0,2	4395983	6.62	239.5 5	1603.72
8	KALI MANT AN BARA T	2013	102,41	67412498 .73	14648322 .59	64. 30	893,5	40 4,5	4395983	9.48	243.0 3	1889.39
8	KALI MANT AN BARA T	2014	50,01	74326099 .85	17080086 .16	64. 89	596,5	42 8,7	4395983	9.38	508.0 9	1862.44
8	KALI	2015	-	80934225	19309344	65.	495,8	26	4395983	6.17	653.4	1989.63

	MANTAN BARAT		195,72	.86	.49	59		7,0			9	
8	KALIMANTAN BARAT	2016	110,02	88906169 .78	18998423 .90	65. 88	459	25 5,7	4395983	3.88	653.4 9	1989.63
8	KALIMANTAN BARAT	2017	109,41	96802975 .14	20593759 .26	66. 26	431,3	22 2,0	4395983	3.86	603.4 9	2252.06
8	KALIMANTAN BARAT	2018	55,6	10293846 1.37	22306179 .83	66. 98	367,5	28 1,0	4395983	3.99	778.8 2	2373.12
8	KALIMANTAN BARAT	2019	9,63	11074843 7.24	24867885 .32	67. 65	413,5	10 7,5	4395983	3.99	804.9 2	2572.69
8	KALIMANTAN BARAT	2020	0	11057271 3.95	26104494 .27	67. 66	572,8	10 1,2	4395983	3.99	804.9 2	2572.69
9	KALIMANTAN TENGAH	2010	0	25562603 .09	8217457. 86	65. 96	3659, 7	86 8,5	2212089	9.49	89.05	649.95
9	KALIMANTAN TENGAH	2011	247	28486203 .75	9411470. 39	66. 38	5715, 5	1 238,5	2212089	5.28	89.05	649.95
9	KALIMANTAN TENGAH	2012	137,41	31670844 .20	10761622 .42	66. 66	5204, 6	1 233,6	2212089	6.73	79.01	752.34
9	KALIMANTAN TENGAH	2013	102,41	34618909 .41	11907576 .72	67. 41	5654, 7	1 328,8	2212089	6.45	76.00	854.78
9	KALIMANTAN TENGAH	2014	50,01	38029999 .71	13513158 .06	67. 77	4493, 8	1 192,6	2212089	6.63	76.00	970.16
9	KALIMANTAN TENGAH	2015	- 195,72	42418617 .95	15744457 .12	68. 53	8144, 9	1 712,0	2212089	4.20	242.1 5	1048.64
9	KALIMANTAN	2016	110,02	47357348 .11	16218632 .57	69. 13	7668, 7	99 2,4	2212089	1.91	242.1 5	1048.64

	AN TENG AH												
9	KALI MANT AN TENG AH	2017	109,41	52183860 .42	17283856 .20	69. 79	10928 ,2	1 199,2	2212089	3.11	356.7 6	1134.95	
9	KALI MANT AN TENG AH	2018	55,6	56315879 .35	18738116 .92	70. 42	11564 ,5	2 142,8	2212089	3.68	485.4 8	1223.79	
9	KALI MANT AN TENG AH	2019	9,63	61920206 .68	19927038 .58	70. 91	10499 ,2	1 641,7	2212089	3.68	256.5 1	1358.77	
9	KALI MANT AN TENG AH	2020	0	64126131 .26	21754735 .17	71. 05	8697, 3	1 237,3	2212089	3.68	256.5 1	1358.77	
10	KALI MANT AN SELA TAN	2010	0	40777814 .72	10657862 .63	65. 20	6339, 7	1 419,4	3626616	9.06	306.8 2	1467.13	
10	KALI MANT AN SELA TAN	2011	247	44995001 .57	11626595 .46	65. 89	9617	2 593,7	3626616	3.98	306.8 2	1467.13	
10	KALI MANT AN SELA TAN	2012	137,41	48832898 .72	13541402 .39	66. 68	9476, 5	2 752,7	3626616	5.96	468.9 2	1688.44	
10	KALI MANT AN SELA TAN	2013	102,41	52998241 .86	14981234 .14	67. 17	8481, 7	2 478,1	3626616	6.98	478.3 2	1880.66	
10	KALI MANT AN SELA TAN	2014	50,01	58574581 .04	16030654 .93	67. 63	7931, 2	2 127,9	3626616	7.16	645.4 1	2092.23	
10	KALI MANT AN SELA TAN	2015	- 195,72	63942093 .65	18230518 .16	68. 38	35644 ,4	1 071,1	3626616	5.03	1671. 13	2187.64	
10	KALI MANT AN SELA TAN	2016	110,02	69096597 .17	19094318 .98	69. 05	3327, 2	69 8,2	3626616	3.68	1671. 13	2187.64	
10	KALI MANT AN	2017	109,41	74554961 .35	19758967 .90	69. 65	4373, 3	1 141,9	3626616	3.82	1831. 94	2391.87	

	SELA TAN												
10	KALI MANTAN SELA TAN	2018	55,6	80467494 .75	21248561 .97	70. 17	5054, 2	1 143,7	3626616	2.63	2790. 84	2602.39	
10	KALI MANTAN SELA TAN	2019	9,63	86960666 .27	22162649 .33	70. 72	4693, 4	1 042,4	3626616	2.63	3050. 81	2819.16	
10	KALI MANTAN SELA TAN	2020	0	87613070 .43	21946711 .15	70. 91	3293, 5	48 5,6	3626616	2.63	3050. 81	2819.16	
10	KALI MANTAN TIMUR	2010	0	51059096 .90	14013989 .57	71. 31	21823	5 863,5	3553143	7.00	381.2 8	2277.22	
10	KALI MANTAN TIMUR	2011	247	57527377 .45	15108733 .82	72. 02	33030 ,8	6 828,2	3553143	6.23	381.2 8	2277.22	
10	KALI MANTAN TIMUR	2012	137,41	65493370 .52	17342813 .74	72. 62	28747	7 801,2	3553143	4.81	424.8 8	2502.32	
10	KALI MANTAN TIMUR	2013	102,41	73396421 .73	20281615 .33	73. 21	26109 ,5	8 765,9	3553143	10.37	518.5 0	2731.58	
10	KALI MANTAN TIMUR	2014	50,01	80180286 .67	23523174 .00	73. 82	21475 ,2	7 791,3	3553143	6.74	977.5 6	2815.55	
10	KALI MANTAN TIMUR	2015	- 195,72	86786223 .85	25949715 .17	74. 17	12546	4 567,8	3553143	4.24	1053. 03	3007.30	
10	KALI MANTAN TIMUR	2016	110,02	91536846 .47	23578343 .61	74. 59	9175, 5	3 125,5	3553143	2.83	1053. 03	3007.30	
10	KALI MANTAN TIMUR	2017	109,41	96807319 .69	21596788 .97	75. 12	11349 ,1	2 489,3	3553143	3.69	1437. 95	3418.33	
10	KALI MANTAN TIMUR	2018	55,6	10258419 6.19	23760619 .51	75. 83	11576 ,2	3 418,7	3553143	3.32	1192. 23	3637.27	

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10	KALI MANTAN TIMUR	2019	9,63	10976765 6.05	26298927 .52	76. 61	9941, 9	1 555,8	3553143	3.32	785.8 5	3952.88
10	KALI MANTAN TIMUR	2020	0	11118375 1.56	26163828 .57	76. 24	8149, 6	1 168,6	3553143	3.32	785.8 5	3952.88
10	KALI MANTAN UTARA	2010	0	6848352. 68	3327520. 96	-	453,8	44, 9	0	7.92	31.22	-
10	KALI MANTAN UTARA	2011	247	7827140. 83	3470878. 56	-	392	68, 4	0	6.43	31.22	-
10	KALI MANTAN UTARA	2012	137,41	8909550. 86	4000676. 90	-	5204, 6	70, 0	0	5.99	31.22	-
10	KALI MANTAN UTARA	2013	102,41	4000676. 90	5123223. 18	67. 99	5654, 7	93, 7	0	10.35	31.22	180.73
10	KALI MANTAN UTARA	2014	50,01	5123223. 18	6586508. 87	68. 64	4493, 8	33, 0	0	11.91	84.82	199.37
10	KALI MANTAN UTARA	2015	- 195,72	12243723 .32	6884835. 73	68. 76	8144, 9	11, 0	0	3.42	99.82	206.50
10	KALI MANTAN UTARA	2016	110,02	13041725 .87	6722185. 09	69. 20	7668, 7	12, 3	0	4.31	99.82	206.50
10	KALI MANTAN UTARA	2017	109,41	13747600 .94	6184828. 23	69. 84	10928 ,2	15, 3	0	2.77	73.60	180.59
10	KALI MANTAN UTARA	2018	55,6	14608034 .44	6595911. 72	70. 56	11564 ,5	37, 2	0	5.00	238.2 0	183.32
10	KALI MANTAN UTARA	2019	9,63	16004279 .42	7184812. 63	71. 15	10499 ,2	20, 2	0	5.00	238.2 0	264.55

10	KALI MANTAN UTARA	2020	0	15997555 .15	7103647. 47	70. 63	8697, 3	46, 9	0	5.00	238.2 0	264.55
11	SULA WESI UTARA	2010	0	25425197 .31	8422590. 91	67. 83	373,6	70, 8	2270596	6.28	202.0 6	986.62
11	SULA WESI UTARA	2011	247	28031771 .92	10077730 .91	68. 31	744	14 4,4	2270596	0.67	202.0 6	986.62
11	SULA WESI UTARA	2012	137,41	30908682 .00	11110270 .30	69. 04	941,8	12 2,6	2270596	6.04	458.3 2	1087.08
11	SULA WESI UTARA	2013	102,41	32781303 .72	12349804 .59	69. 49	665,4	10 6,5	2270596	8.12	345.1 9	1192.52
11	SULA WESI UTARA	2014	50,01	36541276 .27	14016073 .31	69. 96	833,2	11 7,7	2270596	9.67	350.4 5	1240.32
11	SULA WESI UTARA	2015	- 195,72	41806112 .12	16267833 .70	70. 39	676,7	68, 9	2270596	5.56	358.0 3	1302.58
11	SULA WESI UTARA	2016	110,02	45568217 .29	17219164 .56	71. 05	693,4	12 2,1	2270596	0.35	358.0 3	1302.58
11	SULA WESI UTARA	2017	109,41	49364986 .52	19033744 .10	71. 66	627,9	65, 6	2270596	2.44	580.7 7	1544.87
11	SULA WESI UTARA	2018	55,6	52740064 .07	21146537 .13	72. 20	520,3	98, 5	2270596	3.83	557.2 2	1676.89
11	SULA WESI UTARA	2019	9,63	57744090 .60	22182004 .38	72. 99	296,4	13 3,5	2270596	3.83	295.5 0	1787.87
11	SULA WESI UTARA	2020	0	57272630 .53	22416894 .57	72. 93	320,6	87, 7	2270596	3.83	295.5 0	1787.87
11	GORO NTAL O	2010	0	9691201. 35	3642768. 28	62. 65	212,1	19, 4	1040164	7.43	33.20	236.52
11	GORO NTAL O	2011	247	10894675 .25	4277192. 00	63. 48	584	89, 9	1040164	4.08	33.20	236.52
11	GORO NTAL O	2012	137,41	12229032 .64	4843216. 78	64. 16	805,9	16 5,7	1040164	5.31	31.44	293.13
11	GORO NTAL O	2013	102,41	13717787 .55	5497584. 18	64. 70	925,4	27 9,5	1040164	5.84	31.44	328.40

11	GORONTALO	2014	50,01	15403967.17	6077544.61	65.17	306,3	282,4	1040164	6.14	64.73	366.08
11	GORONTALO	2015	-195,72	17483651.60	6809069.25	65.86	1469,5	510,7	1040164	4.30	31.49	398.82
11	GORONTALO	2016	110,02	19300321.72	7215175.33	66.29	2345,3	603,9	1040164	1.30	31.49	398.82
11	GORONTALO	2017	109,41	21233931.10	7804161.78	67.01	3938,8	824,1	1040164	4.34	56.83	460.13
11	GORONTALO	2018	55,6	23234274.80	8245792.68	67.71	6480,5	1294,9	1040164	2.15	57.91	503.49
11	GORONTALO	2019	9,63	25432278.57	8725060.00	68.49	7554,5	1590,2	1040164	2.15	57.41	543.84
11	GORONTALO	2020	0	25860313.11	8246397.97	68.68	9986,5	1343,2	1040164	2.15	57.41	543.84
11	SULAWESI TENG GARA	2010	0	25438020.25	7712647.84	65.99	461,9	19,4	2232586	3.87	91.30	441.08
11	SULAWESI TENG GARA	2011	247	28223869.28	9683828.69	66.52	758,4	89,9	2232586	5.09	91.30	441.08
11	SULAWESI TENG GARA	2012	137,41	32397970.95	10036522.54	67.07	594,2	165,7	2232586	5.25	125.24	528.42
11	SULAWESI TENG GARA	2013	102,41	36489259.48	10897203.38	67.55	409,2	279,5	2232586	5.92	129.24	621.64
11	SULAWESI TENG GARA	2014	50,01	40339623.11	11717190.11	68.07	278,3	282,4	2232586	7.40	233.07	670.71
11	SULAWESI TENG GARA	2015	-195,72	44092255.44	13103283.67	68.75	128,9	510,7	2232586	1.64	127.47	703.59
11	SULAWESI TENG GARA	2016	110,02	48316552.74	14220093.00	69.31	107,1	603,9	2232586	3.07	127.47	703.59
11	SULAWESI TENG GARA	2017	109,41	53297732.04	15897054.71	69.86	141	824,1	2232586	2.96	296.59	850.70
11	SULAWESI TENG GARA	2018	55,6	58267074.66	17403784.03	70.61	286,1	1294,9	2232586	2.55	293.38	911.73
11	SULAWESI TENG GARA	2019	9,63	63466417.86	18878976.19	71.20	319,1	1590,2	2232586	2.55	148.92	986.89

11	SULA WESI TENG GARA	2020	0	64390663 .53	18887975 .66	71. 45	119,4	1 343,2	2232586	2.55	148.9 2	986.89
12	SULA WESI TENG AH	2010	0	31595755 .09	8009483. 78	63. 29	320,4	11, 8	2635009	6.40	175.7 3	574.71
12	SULA WESI TENG AH	2011	247	34943533 .27	9169333. 77	64. 27	147	11, 9	2635009	4.47	175.7 3	574.71
12	SULA WESI TENG AH	2012	137,41	39208294 .30	10425364 .46	65. 00	85,1	2,7	2635009	5.87	189.1 8	686.19
12	SULA WESI TENG AH	2013	102,41	43987610 .28	11783906 .76	65. 79	38,1,8	15, 5	2635009	7.57	198.0 9	758.70
12	SULA WESI TENG AH	2014	50,01	50558562 .97	50558562 .97	66. 43	118,6	42, 1	2635009	8.85	422.4 1	865.77
12	SULA WESI TENG AH	2015	- 195,72	55834296 .84	15369757 .18	66. 76	340,2	28, 4	2635009	4.17	421.1 2	948.78
12	SULA WESI TENG AH	2016	110,02	60961078 .61	16210691 .37	67. 47	364,4	9,4	2635009	1.49	421.1 2	948.78
12	SULA WESI TENG AH	2017	109,41	66440683 .51	17545237 .69	68. 11	404,7	3,1	2635009	4.33	490.6 2	1068.79
12	SULA WESI TENG AH	2018	55,6	72976447 .27	17936010 .91	68. 88	457,8	4,4	2635009	6.46	1718. 47	1171.08
12	SULA WESI TENG AH	2019	9,63	79421563 .15	19792709 .68	69. 50	467,7	11, 6	2635009	6.46	1746. 21	1146.23
12	SULA WESI TENG AH	2020	0	77624593 .72	20086146 .18	69. 55	507,8	2,9	2635009	6.46	1746. 21	1146.23
12	SULA WESI SELA TAN	2010	0	99661110 .94	20578073 .82	66. 00	2312	95 5,6	8034776	6.82	625.9 6	3246.42
12	SULA WESI SELA TAN	2011	247	11354723 0.59	23491337 .09	66. 65	1898, 6	1 364,5	8034776	2.87	625.9 6	3246.42
12	SULA WESI SELA TAN	2012	137,41	12968794 7.32	12968794 7.32	67. 26	1516, 6	1 180,8	8034776	4.57	1045. 81	3639.63
12	SULA	2013	102,41	14664307	28718940	67.	1550,	1	8034776	6.24	1084.	4156.49

	WESI SELA TAN			3.88	.13	92	9	189,8			85	
12	SULA WESI SELA TAN	2014	50,01	16565221 5.83	31774365 .70	68. 49	1736, 1	81 3,6	8034776	8.51	968.9 2	4339.22
12	SULA WESI SELA TAN	2015	- 195,72	18558554 3.03	36396615 .59	69. 15	568,4	61 2,1	8034776	5.18	1232. 35	4479.46
12	SULA WESI SELA TAN	2016	110,02	20436874 9.91	37399191 .96	69. 76	513,6	66 5,4	8034776	3.18	1232. 35	4479.46
12	SULA WESI SELA TAN	2017	109,41	22540455 4.58	39393172 .37	70. 34	265,1	8 328,6	8034776	4.48	1450. 85	5172.50
12	SULA WESI SELA TAN	2018	55,6	25114750 4.70	44827507 .85	70. 90	395,8	1 013,3	8034776	3.48	2953. 94	5472.48
12	SULA WESI SELA TAN	2019	9,63	27446363 8.68	49429293 .61	71. 66	828,2	97 7,6	8034776	3.48	2995. 60	5945.56
12	SULA WESI SELA TAN	2020	0	27859401 2.06	48633679 .90	71. 93	818,6	74 7,6	8034776	3.48	2995. 60	5945.56
12	SULA WESI BARA T	2010	0	10453566 .60	3192723. 39	59. 74	24	19, 4	1158651	5.12	6.49	151.52
12	SULA WESI BARA T	2011	247	11733846 .66	3732160. 42	60. 63	2,7	89, 9	1158651	4.91	6.49	151.52
12	SULA WESI BARA T	2012	137,41	12726692 .87	4267713. 89	61. 01	0	16 5,7	1158651	3.28	6.39	177.63
12	SULA WESI BARA T	2013	102,41	14014432 .23	4694733. 05	61. 53	0	27 9,5	1158651	5.91	12.39	207.59
12	SULA WESI BARA T	2014	50,01	15261635 .11	5153208. 58	62. 24	152	28 2,4	1158651	7.88	11.68	238.03
12	SULA WESI BARA T	2015	- 195,72	17219020 .72	6026226. 40	62. 96	0	51 0,7	1158651	5.07	3.22	258.70
12	SULA WESI BARA T	2016	110,02	18883977 .76	6781949. 00	63. 60	0	60 3,9	1158651	2.23	3.22	258.70
12	SULA WESI	2017	109,41	20388814 .62	7342269. 61	64. 30	0,2	82 4,1	1158651	3.79	3.22	312.89

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12	SULA WESI BARA T	2018	55,6	22146397 .19	7902508. 45	65. 10	0	1 294,9	1158651	1.80	63.22	345.28
12	SULA WESI BARA T	2019	9,63	23261840 .60	8087420. 28	65. 73	1,4	1 590,2	1158651	1.80	67.77	380.08
12	SULA WESI BARA T	2020	0	24190133 .25	7371770. 45	66. 11	2,1	1 343,2	1158651	1.80	67.77	380.08
13	MALU KU	2010	0	12502864 .76	7126877. 38	64. 27	165,3	33 6,3	1533506	8.78	134.6 5	336.69
13	MALU KU	2011	247	13812754 .73	9245920. 57	64. 75	195	36 1,2	1533506	2.85	134.6 5	336.69
13	MALU KU	2012	137,41	16230482 .46	16230482 .46	65. 43	243,8	42 9,1	1533506	6.73	135.0 6	397.49
13	MALU KU	2013	102,41	18167297 .01	10831192 .56	66. 09	209,4	35 7,9	1533506	8.81	147.6 1	469.96
13	MALU KU	2014	50,01	21226234 .07	11825587 .55	66. 74	152,2	39 2,1	1533506	6.81	211.7 9	480.08
13	MALU KU	2015	- 195,72	24048412 .34	13775000 .51	67. 05	42,8	29 7,4	1533506	5.92	236.7 6	509.51
13	MALU KU	2016	110,02	26646284 .39	14900712 .08	67. 60	121,1	30 7,1	1533506	3.28	236.7 6	509.51
13	MALU KU	2017	109,41	28656669 .59	15638089 .97	68. 19	95,8	49 5,2	1533506	-0.05	263.3 7	463.05
13	MALU KU	2018	55,6	30096578 .75	30096578 .75	68. 87	192,7	64 2,7	1533506	3.53	297.0 6	597.37
13	MALU KU	2019	9,63	32753525 .98	16456585 .84	69. 45	245,2	51 5,8	1533506	3.53	363.4 3	519.13
13	MALU KU	2020	0	33008212 .31	16738236 .08	69. 49	186,3	50 3,9	1533506	3.53	363.4 3	519.13
13	MALU KU UTAR A	2010	0	9638268. 05	4215399. 12	62. 79	309,9	24, 0	1038087	5.32	62.04	204.67
13	MALU KU UTAR A	2011	247	10566933 .36	5184808. 38	63. 19	547,3	20, 3	1038087	4.52	62.04	204.67
13	MALU KU UTAR A	2012	137,41	11546049 .48	6022774. 64	63. 93	446	5,3	1038087	3.29	44.60	235.88
13	MALU KU UTAR A	2013	102,41	12748837 .48	6903319. 10	64. 78	645	3,2	1038087	9.78	49.60	259.10
13	MALU KU UTAR A	2014	50,01	13957149 .41	7965612. 06	65. 18	52,4	5,1	1038087	9.34	65.70	309.37
13	MALU KU UTAR A	2015	- 195,72	15464567 .77	8856577. 32	65. 91	40	40, 8	1038087	4.52	73.81	329.44

13	MALU KU UTAR A	2016	110,02	16943243 .12	9222776. 71	66. 63	36,1	10 2,9	1038087	1.91	73.81	329.44
13	MALU KU UTAR A	2017	109,41	18359622 .74	9893536. 19	67. 20	101,1	100,9	1038087	1.97	124.3 8	237.12
13	MALU KU UTAR A	2018	55,6	19996617 .07	19996617 .07	67. 76	194,5	156,5	1038087	4.12	88.36	401.48
13	MALU KU UTAR A	2019	9,63	21400016 .62	12158565 .81	68. 70	245	35 5,2	1038087	4.12	120.2 7	537.52
13	MALU KU UTAR A	2020	0	21697152 .93	11668834 .91	68. 49	286,7	40 4,6	1038087	4.12	120.2 7	537.52
13	PAPU A BARA T	2010	0	10906686 .08	6781745. 40	59. 60	1690, 8	70, 7	760422	4.68	55.67	305.08
13	PAPU A BARA T	2011	247	11507209 .97	7792314. 61	59. 90	3027, 2	60, 6	760422	3.64	55.67	305.08
13	PAPU A BARA T	2012	137,41	12299650 .83	9037898. 58	60. 30	3652	19, 5	760422	4.88	58.67	346.65
13	PAPU A BARA T	2013	102,41	13375761 .35	10296201 .40	60. 91	3518, 3	33, 5	760422	4.63	66.64	383.99
13	PAPU A BARA T	2014	50,01	14716998 .61	11594723 .56	61. 28	3894	32, 6	760422	5.70	102.8 0	430.63
13	PAPU A BARA T	2015	- 195,72	16573309 .27	12982662 .64	61. 73	2768, 1	71, 6	760422	2.77	112.7 6	455.58
13	PAPU A BARA T	2016	110,02	18549037 .83	14383111 .84	62. 21	1852, 3	10 5,4	760422	5.75	112.7 6	455.58
13	PAPU A BARA T	2017	109,41	20483626 .43	14893736 .70	62. 99	2050, 6	10 7,8	760422	1.78	403.5 9	533.47
13	PAPU A BARA T	2018	55,6	22513251 .69	15413561 .42	63. 74	2986, 6	19 3,5	760422	6.02	121.0 9	569.02
13	PAPU A BARA T	2019	9,63	24598065 .60	17256062 .45	64. 70	2537, 6	39 9,8	760422	6.02	147.9 2	510.01
13	PAPU	2020	0	24681138	16704529	65.	2040,	42	760422	6.02	147.9	510.01

	A BARA T			.44	.27	09	7	1,7			2	
13	PAPU A	2010	0	39252306 .16	18189543 .25	54. 45	5042	94 5,7	2833381	4.48	91.64	522.80
13	PAPU A	2011	247	44810410 .89	20351449 .70	55. 01	3664, 3	1 119,5	2833381	3.40	91.64	522.80
13	PAPU A	2012	137,41	50164829 .26	22734799 .38	55. 55	2146, 3	1 025,7	2833381	4.52	96.25	600.67
13	PAPU A	2013	102,41	57323963 .55	26176235 .14	56. 25	2747, 7	50 7,1	2833381	8.27	106.3 0	713.26
13	PAPU A	2014	50,01	65393761 .18	30457008 .67	56. 75	1493, 2	1 016,2	2833381	7.98	242.4 4	724.78
13	PAPU A	2015	- 195,72	71699211 .76	34069654 .56	57. 25	1940, 7	69 3,8	2833381	2.79	271.1 4	763.32
13	PAPU A	2016	110,02	80062232 .52	36238896 .82	58. 05	1988, 9	71 6,9	2833381	4.13	271.1 4	763.32
13	PAPU A	2017	109,41	87903533 .79	38810543 .43	59. 09	2489	36 2,0	2833381	2.41	128.1 9	868.01
13	PAPU A	2018	55,6	98110317 .91	40859615 .11	60. 06	4003, 1	39 8,4	2833381	6.70	550.0 2	916.96
13	PAPU A	2019	9,63	10536180 3.20	43898192 .85	60. 84	1384, 4	48 6,4	2833381	6.70	580.6 4	1057.65
13	PAPU A	2020	0	10103824 5.83	44100358 .32	60. 44	2128, 7	47 5,5	2833381	6.70	580.6 4	1057.65
14	34 PROVI NSI	2010	0	37857746 62.09	61817799 2.00	66. 53	15777 9,1	5 663,3	2376413 26	6.96	3559 6.74	158694. 89
14	34 PROVI NSI	2011	247	42246188 38.30	70950153 3.02	67. 09	20349 6,6	7 435,6	2376413 26	3.79	3559 6.74	158694. 89
14	34 PROVI NSI	2012	137,41	47116739 63.82	80750450 5.19	67. 70	19002 0,3	1 689,5	2376413 26	4.30	4484 1.54	174341. 92
14	34 PROVI NSI	2013	102,41	52702867 56.16	90404655 7.38	68. 31	182,5 51,8	6 628,7	2376413 26	8.38	4547 6.31	188342. 41
14	34 PROVI NSI	2014	50,01	58303087 68.94	98034223 5.59	68. 90	17598 0	8 178,8	2376413 26	8.36	5301 5.70	199028. 08
14	34 PROVI NSI	2015	- 195,72	64299997 03.23	11137734 53.19	69. 55	15036 6,3	2 694,8	2376413 26	3.35	5462 4.17	204279. 97
14	34 PROVI NSI	2016	110,02	69881951 76.70	11668861 02.93	70. 18	14513 4	5 652,8	2376413 26	3.02	5462 4.17	204279. 97
14	34 PROVI NSI	2017	109,41	75797790 32.04	12483508 23.73	70. 81	16882 8,2	6 985,5	2376413 26	3.61	5864 7.49	226014. 06
14	34 PROVI NSI	2018	55,6	82357393 35.27	13646881 11.84	71. 39	18001 2,7	8 711,3	2376413 26	3.13	6394 6.60	239012. 04
14	34 PROVI NSI	2019	9,63	89108920 62.96	14388893 91.65	71. 92	16768 3	1 275,7	2376413 26	3.13	6660 7.83	247653. 33
14	34 PROVI NSI	2020	0	14	14753878 03.30	71. 94	16319 1,8	14 568,8	2376413 26	3.13	6660 7.83	247653. 33

Table 3 The Table Sof Scoring from each Variables

KOD SUB PUL AU/ KEP ULA UAN	NAMA PROVIN SI	TA HU N	CARBO N EMISSI ON	HOUS EHOL D COMS UPTIO N	GOVER NMENT T SPENDI NG	EDUC ATIO N SPAC ES	INDU STRI AL ESTA TES	TRA DE CEN TRES	HOU SING ESTA TES	OFFI CE BUIL DING S	GRE EN PUB LIC OPE N SPA CES	GRE Y PRIV AT OPEN SPA CES
GRO UP OF PRO VIN CES	PROVIN CES	BU DG ET YE ARS	ENVIRO NMENT SUSTAI NABIL ITY	LEVE L OF WEAL TH		IPM	EKSP OR	IMP OR	PEND UDU K	INFL ATIO N	TOW ERS	NET WOR KS
1	ACEH	2010	0	554384 32.71	1957217 5.74	67.09	1 326,3	223,6	44944 10	4.64	159.2 6	1579.7 7
1	ACEH	2011	247	594642 14.13	2280417 7.33	67.45	1 406,3	345,7	44944 10	3.32	159.2 6	1579.7 7
1	ACEH	2012	137,41	635717 82.01	2515397 5.63	67.81	1 197,2	546,1	44944 10	0.06	156.9 3	1755.0 6
1	ACEH	2013	102,41	688172 14.34	2965593 3.43	68.30	930,4	483,5	44944 10	6.39	128.5 4	1815.0 4
1	ACEH	2014	50,01	741852 21.08	3146352 5.27	68.81	501,2	459,2	44944 10	7.83	201.2 5	1965.5 5
1	ACEH	2015	-195,72	798511 30.37	3518003 4.54	69.45	38,8	1213, 1	44944 10	1.27	232.1 0	2119.0 0
1	ACEH	2016	110,02	856391 66.37	3180269 5.62	70.00	0,0	1059, 2	44944 10	3.13	232.1 0	2119.0 0
1	ACEH	2017	109,41	917689 57.81	3405801 8.76	70.60	0,0	1106, 4	44944 10	4.86	224.2 7	2409.1 1
1	ACEH	2018	55,6	970539 93.71	3542302 3.59	71.19	0,8	1656, 7	44944 10	1.93	221.1 3	2587.7 1
1	ACEH	2019	9,63	103294 496.91	3812141 3.50	71.90	4,8	1593, 1	44944 10	1.93	239.5 5	2781.5 0
1	ACEH	2020	0	104428 468.72	3529982 8.62	71.99	0,3	1569, 7	44944 10	1.93	239.5 5	2781.5 0
1	SUMATE RA UTARA	2010	0	178332 312.83	2570761 9.69	67.09	7 429,0	3296, 3	12982 204	7.65	2450. 67	7194.0 3
1	SUMATE RA UTARA	2011	247	198151 435.05	2956852 0.01	67.34	10 057,7	4606, 5	12982 204	3.54	2450. 67	7194.0 3
1	SUMATE RA UTARA	2012	137,41	222744 922.75	3338662 0.71	67.74	8 871,9	4775, 6	12982 204	3.79	3501. 67	7809.3 2
1	SUMATE RA UTARA	2013	102,41	251415 642.84	3752321 5.11	68.36	7 982,3	4826, 3	12982 204	10.09	3625. 32	7917.2 4
1	SUMATE RA UTARA	2014	50,01	281431 384.00	4079856 0.90	68.87	7 808,1	4777, 7	12982 204	8.24	4116. 45	8271.0 1
1	SUMATE RA UTARA	2015	-195,72	306071 858.51	4396045 3.55	69.51	6 618,1	3771, 1	12982 204	3.32	4241. 54	8703.6 7
1	SUMATE RA UTARA	2016	110,02	333511 725.39	4607271 5.84	70.00	6 768,8	3669, 9	12982 204	6.60	4241. 54	8703.6 7
1	SUMATE RA UTARA	2017	109,41	364057 391.98	5183812 8.31	70.57	8 111,6	4392, 7	12982 204	3.18	4832. 95	9671.4 8

1	SUMATE RA UTARA	2018	55,6	397422 809.82	5629876 5.87	71.18	7 743,3	5206, 3	12982 204	1.00	5017. 05	10445. 02
1	SUMATE RA UTARA	2019	9,63	430766 355.21	5741717 8.40	71.74	6 786,8	4256, 6	12982 204	1.00	5679. 04	8324.8 6
1	SUMATE RA UTARA	2020	0	424494 987.37	5625827 2.38	71.77	6 921,4	3786, 1	12982 204	1.00	5679. 04	8324.8 6
2	SUMATE RA BARAT	2010	0	594217 25.64	1429811 1.53	67.25	2 214,6	223,6	48469 09	7.84	33.45	2403.1 0
2	SUMATE RA BARAT	2011	247	656681 66.97	1585643 6.96	67.81	3 030,0	345,7	48469 09	5.37	33.45	2403.1 0
2	SUMATE RA BARAT	2012	137,41	721918 23.49	1767553 4.77	68.36	2 362,9	546,1	48469 09	4.16	32.93	2649.0 8
2	SUMATE RA BARAT	2013	102,41	802655 41.43	1968367 5.57	68.91	2 208,6	483,5	48469 09	10.87	32.91	2712.8 5
2	SUMATE RA BARAT	2014	50,01	882826 01.42	2162246 7.67	69.36	2 105,4	459,2	48469 09	11.90	72.67	3005.2 6
2	SUMATE RA BARAT	2015	-195,72	965318 30.74	2425571 8.84	69.98	1 753,1	1213, 1	48469 09	0.85	305.1 5	3063.2 8
2	SUMATE RA BARAT	2016	110,02	103844 966.07	2551159 8.02	70.73	1 708,1	1059, 2	48469 09	5.02	305.1 5	3063.2 8
2	SUMATE RA BARAT	2017	109,41	112706 034.50	2689412 4.14	71.24	2 045,5	1106, 4	48469 09	2.11	283.0 3	3415.2 9
2	SUMATE RA BARAT	2018	55,6	122631 948.77	2899400 8.80	71.73	1 598,1	1656, 7	48469 09	2.55	59.84	3496.1 8
2	SUMATE RA BARAT	2019	9,63	133817 325.72	3110349 3.49	72.39	1 337,7	1593, 1	48469 09	2.55	821.6 8	3445.0 8
2	SUMATE RA BARAT	2020	0	130886 399.01	2885252 3.81	72.38	1 531,3	1569, 7	48469 09	2.55	821.6 8	3445.0 8
2	RIAU	2010	0	107024 045.49	1591752 3.93	68.65	855,0	504,7	55383 67	7.00	111.2 3	2361.1 5
2	RIAU	2011	247	128523 814.32	1834481 4.53	68.90	594,6	1175, 2	55383 67	5.09	111.2 3	2361.1 5
2	RIAU	2012	137,41	149001 458.78	1975038 3.10	69.15	552,0	1084, 9	55383 67	3.35	157.6 7	2723.8 1
2	RIAU	2013	102,41	171473 394.95	2122780 1.18	69.91	197,8	1064, 5	55383 67	8.83	175.4 8	3597.4 4
2	RIAU	2014	50,01	197162 815.61	2056289 7.64	70.33	021,3	778,1	55383 67	8.53	172.6 2	3338.3 3
2	RIAU	2015	-195,72	222173 095.96	2346283 6.56	70.84	416,4	492,5	55383 67	2.71	173.8 0	3586.4 5
2	RIAU	2016	110,02	241264 481.36	2554753 6.97	71.20	894,4	332,7	55383 67	4.19	173.8 0	3586.4 5
2	RIAU	2017	109,41	259002 304.12	2676071 5.29	71.79	979,7	391,2	55383 67	4.07	353.7 6	4069.9 3
2	RIAU	2018	55,6	272940 741.94	2773383 3.57	72.44	506,6	436,9	55383 67	2.54	317.0 9	4377.2 1

2	RIAU	2019	9,63	287375 389.50	3152967 7.36	73.00	8 961,7	502,4	55383 67	2.54	373.2 2	4646.7 9
2	RIAU	2020	0	288576 671.18	3280265 8.50	72.71	10 403,9	310,1	55383 67	2.54	373.2 2	4646.7 9
2	KEP. RIAU	2010	0	412274 35.61	6740477. 81	71.13	8 328,1	118,2	16791 63	6.17	301.4 7	2010.3 0
2	KEP. RIAU	2011	247	458187 61.02	7599014. 19	71.61	11 346,3	1728, 4	16791 63	3.32	301.4 7	2010.3 0
2	KEP. RIAU	2012	137,41	504226 24.19	8661512. 44	72.36	10 462,8	2730, 5	16791 63	3.92	371.4 3	2190.0 4
2	KEP. RIAU	2013	102,41	567727 21.87	9780476. 89	73.02	11 618,7	2417, 3	16791 63	10.09	381.2 1	2421.9 2
2	KEP. RIAU	2014	50,01	637255 21.84	1096268 7.42	73.40	9 116,8	2296, 2	16791 63	7.49	736.4 8	2618.4 8
2	KEP. RIAU	2015	-195,72	730641 67.14	1238439 6.32	73.75	7 549,8	6065, 7	16791 63	2.46	736.8 0	2694.7 9
2	KEP. RIAU	2016	110,02	828620 14.41	1381027 1.14	73.99	7 411,7	5295, 9	16791 63	3.06	736.8 0	2694.7 9
2	KEP. RIAU	2017	109,41	924441 10.41	1473714 5.11	74.45	7 232,2	5531, 9	16791 63	3.37	882.5 4	2823.1 7
2	KEP. RIAU	2018	55,6	992605 06.76	1473268 8.97	74.84	7 883,9	8283, 3	16791 63	2.36	969.6 2	2990.4 4
2	KEP. RIAU	2019	9,63	106928 431.18	1513064 6.71	75.48	8 323,7	7965, 5	16791 63	2.36	1005. 94	3346.3 1
2	KEP. RIAU	2020	0	109034 717.89	1495263 3.06	75.59	9 481,8	7848, 5	16791 63	2.36	1005. 94	3346.3 1
3	JAMBI	2010	0	449279 46.05	8024190. 02	65.39	4 184,6	223,6	30922 65	10.52	12.82	1054.1 7
3	JAMBI	2011	247	488382 06.95	9417666. 96	66.14	5 348,9	345,7	30922 65	2.76	12.82	1054.1 7
3	JAMBI	2012	137,41	543171 04.07	1088135 4.28	66.94	5 130,6	546,1	30922 65	4.22	51.38	860.39
3	JAMBI	2013	102,41	595987 82.59	1200022 6.23	67.76	4 646,9	483,5	30922 65	8.74	50.06	955.66
3	JAMBI	2014	50,01	668023 56.10	1300017 3.13	68.24	5 075,4	459,2	30922 65	8.72	51.54	1037.4 5
3	JAMBI	2015	-195,72	718175 41.17	1435313 9.19	68.89	4 086,9	1213, 1	30922 65	1.37	60.37	1083.7 9
3	JAMBI	2016	110,02	769822 64.56	1466395 1.76	69.62	3 683,2	1059, 2	30922 65	4.54	60.37	1083.7 9
3	JAMBI	2017	109,41	832743 10.36	1593663 2.29	69.99	4 650,0	1106, 4	30922 65	2.68	50.57	1176.0 9
3	JAMBI	2018	55,6	893244 93.96	1696826 5.43	70.65	5 033,7	1656, 7	30922 65	3.02	43.13	1219.0 1
3	JAMBI	2019	9,63	963435 29.88	1818986 1.51	71.26	4 331,0	1593, 1	30922 65	3.02	52.77	1932.0 0
3	JAMBI	2020	0	976573 50.81	1784093 9.69	71.29	3 533,6	1569, 7	30922 65	3.02	52.77	1932.0 0
3	SUMATE RA SELATA N	2010	0	124895 817.95	1576966 8.87	64.44	3 513,6	359,3	74503 94	6.02	2380. 92	2978.8 6
3	SUMATE RA SELATA N	2011	247	145350 838.51	1850092 3.96	65.12	5057,4	552,2	74503 94	3.78	2380. 92	2978.8 6
3	SUMATE RA SELATA N	2012	137,41	164016 852.81	2044500 6.34	65.79	4 371,7	506,4	74503 94	2.72	2540. 13	3863.1 2

3	SUMATERA SELATAN	2013	102,41	188289444.92	22542613.64	66.16	3 915,6	551,3	7450394	7.04	2663.26	4162.09
3	SUMATERA SELATAN	2014	50,01	208208393.62	24444772.49	66.75	3 083,8	740	7450394	8.38	3018.06	4477.49
3	SUMATERA SELATAN	2015	-195,72	222487659.92	25889700.37	67.46	2 442,4	1435,5	7450394	3.05	3146.21	4783.02
3	SUMATERA SELATAN	2016	110,02	240977338.86	26313943.52	68.24	1 978,6	977,7	7450394	3.68	3146.21	4783.02
3	SUMATERA SELATAN	2017	109,41	257277121.62	29902575.60	68.86	3 307,4	398,7	7450394	2.85	4494.22	5239.35
3	SUMATERA SELATAN	2018	55,6	277771062.14	32460274.02	69.39	3 734,1	718,7	7450394	2.78	4458.37	5501.26
3	SUMATERA SELATAN	2019	9,63	296904975.01	36686874.55	70.02	3 611,9	503,3	7450394	2.78	4348.66	5258.23
3	SUMATERA SELATAN	2020	0	296555351.56	32465000.46	70.01	3 050,2	936,9	7450394	2.78	4348.66	5258.23
3	BENGKULU	2010	0	17930119.30	5681452.76	65.35	4 184,6	223,6	1715518	9.08	23.24	493.95
3	BENGKULU	2011	247	20297687.14	6214001.11	65.96	5 348,9	345,7	1715518	3.96	23.24	493.95
3	BENGKULU	2012	137,41	23006942.59	6867336.72	66.61	5 130,6	546,1	1715518	4.61	24.04	566.95
3	BENGKULU	2013	102,41	26025111.97	7615202.55	67.50	4 646,9	483,5	1715518	9.94	24.04	641.52
3	BENGKULU	2014	50,01	29476477.89	8850671.55	68.06	5 075,4	459,2	1715518	10.85	43.54	729.64
3	BENGKULU	2015	-195,72	33165076.29	10231616.83	68.59	4 086,9	1213,1	1715518	3.25	25.89	785.43
3	BENGKULU	2016	110,02	36475574.53	11235134.10	69.33	3 683,2	1059,2	1715518	5.00	25.89	785.43
3	BENGKULU	2017	109,41	39301815.64	12028795.14	69.95	4 650,0	1106,4	1715518	3.56	47.20	852.84
3	BENGKULU	2018	55,6	42192931.74	13051200.00	70.64	5 033,7	1656,7	1715518	2.35	51.06	907.45
3	BENGKULU	2019	9,63	45570351.31	13880337.00	71.21	4 331,0	1593,1	1715518	2.35	66.61	955.47
3	BENGKULU	2020	0	46324562.29	14261866.07	71.40	3 533,6	1569,7	1715518	2.35	66.61	955.47
3	KEP. BANGKALU	2010	0	17984595.16	3480126.96	66.02	4 184,6	223,6	1223296	9.36	91.78	535.61
3	KEP. BANGKALU	2011	247	201571	4035831.	66.59	5 348,9	345,7	1223296	5.00	91.78	535.61

	BANGK A BELITU NG			79.83	92				96			
3	KEP. BANGK A BELITU NG	2012	137,41	226508 28.98	4592183. 44	67.21	5 130,6	546,1	12232 96	6.57	111.4 6	664.72
3	KEP. BANGK A BELITU NG	2013	102,41	258338 73.89	5249823. 87	67.92	4 646,9	483,5	12232 96	8.71	106.4 6	721.24
3	KEP. BANGK A BELITU NG	2014	50,01	293322 94.80	5768625. 90	68.27	5 075,4	459,2	12232 96	6.81	234.7 1	805.43
3	KEP. BANGK A BELITU NG	2015	-195,72	325770 16.35	6423805. 18	69.05	4 086,9	1213, 1	12232 96	4.66	314.5 6	861.52
3	KEP. BANGK A BELITU NG	2016	110,02	363670 08.68	7250911. 64	69.55	3 683,2	1059, 2	12232 96	7.78	314.5 6	861.52
3	KEP. BANGK A BELITU NG	2017	109,41	403072 86.64	7691271. 99	69.99	4 650,0	1106, 4	12232 96	2.66	265.4 0	979.19
3	KEP. BANGK A BELITU NG	2018	55,6	441680 89.23	8065844. 82	70.67	5 033,7	1656, 7	12232 96	3.45	285.9 2	1066.3 5
3	KEP. BANGK A BELITU NG	2019	9,63	481744 49.58	8702146. 57	71.30	4 331,0	1593, 1	12232 96	3.45	285.9 2	1166.9 3
3	KEP. BANGK A BELITU NG	2020	0	484636 19.47	8636405. 04	71.47	3 533,6	1569, 7	12232 96	3.45	285.9 2	1166.9 3
4	LAMPU NG	2010	0	896636 83.33	1248370 2.35	63.71	2 467,4	866,7	76084 05	9.95	4.30	2425.9 4
4	LAMPU NG	2011	247	102964 888.38	1451813 7.08	64.20	3 222,6	1247, 8	76084 05	4.24	4.30	2425.9 4
4	LAMPU NG	2012	137,41	114543 996.76	1658705 0.20	64.87	3 698,4	1716, 2	76084 05	4.30	124.7 9	2793.3 6
4	LAMPU NG	2013	102,41	125242 183.96	1842647 6.90	65.73	3 892,3	1552, 9	76084 05	7.56	124.7 9	3182.2 1
4	LAMPU NG	2014	50,01	138464 983.37	2069788 8.09	66.42	3 856,7	1393, 1	76084 05	8.36	121.2 1	3392.4 4
4	LAMPU NG	2015	-195,72	153233 045.67	2397212 5.49	66.95	2 315,9	1474	76084 05	4.65	121.1 2	3571.0 0

4	LAMPUNG	2016	110,02	166902 925.33	2553419 5.80	67.65	1 873,6	1535, 9	76084 05	2.75	121.1 2	3571.0 0
4	LAMPUNG	2017	109,41	182403 658.02	2662797 0.00	68.25	2 132,2	1489, 9	76084 05	3.14	124.3 8	3998.3 0
4	LAMPUNG	2018	55,6	200716 577.65	2787652 0.81	69.02	1 714,2	1365, 3	76084 05	2.92	237.3 8	4257.1 5
4	LAMPUNG	2019	9,63	220341 172.78	2920111 1.71	69.57	1 561,2	1087, 4	76084 05	2.92	237.3 8	4686.0 9
4	LAMPUNG	2020	0	220906 122.30	2938768 7.52	69.69	1 555,9	911,7	76084 05	2.92	237.3 8	4686.0 9
4	BANTEN	2010	0	167676 809.85	1244020 1.36	67.54	938,0	7603, 7	10632 166	6.18	6773. 53	7955.5 4
4	BANTEN	2011	247	181174 857.92	1469053 2.87	68.22	1 106,5	10454 ,3	10632 166	2.78	6773. 53	7955.5 4
4	BANTEN	2012	137,41	201707 891.24	1660626 2.30	68.92	719,9	10424 ,7	10632 166	4.41	11323 .54	8457.8 0
4	BANTEN	2013	102,41	219159 467.84	1867195 4.43	69.47	928,4	10690 ,8	10632 166	9.16	11703 .54	9750.3 7
4	BANTEN	2014	50,01	234035 090.85	1923757 7.65	69.89	895,8	10605 ,5	10632 166	11.27	12873 .34	8562.9 7
4	BANTEN	2015	-195,72	253382 608.28	2111816 7.43	70.27	591,2	7585, 6	10632 166	4.67	12873 .34	8575.1 0
4	BANTEN	2016	110,02	272806 888.68	2289775 6.57	70.96	735,3	6555, 5	10632 166	3.26	12873 .34	8575.1 0
4	BANTEN	2017	109,41	294423 894.26	2461648 8.96	71.42	1 098,9	8135, 2	10632 166	5.17	7443. 90	22557. 53
4	BANTEN	2018	55,6	321788 260.05	2757624 1.87	71.95	1 249,5	9326	10632 166	3.78	8052. 30	23736. 30
4	BANTEN	2019	9,63	348229 115.87	2974484 0.99	72.44	1 227,6	8098, 4	10632 166	3.78	7653. 14	24646. 11
4	BANTEN	2020	0	345666 629.05	2734303 7.41	72.45	938,7	7350, 4	10632 166	3.78	7653. 14	24646. 11
5	DKI JAKARTA A	2010	0	637740 455.50	1369466 57.70	76.31	39519, 8	67716 ,9	96077 87	6.21	1093. 00	35061. 38
5	DKI JAKARTA A	2011	247	713778 798.44	1593020 46.31	76.98	46349	88308 ,7	96077 87	3.97	1093. 00	35061. 38
5	DKI JAKARTA A	2012	137,41	809845 077.26	1832596 52.61	77.53	48018, 2	96406 ,5	96077 87	4.52	1448. 49	38168. 75
5	DKI JAKARTA A	2013	102,41	939160 695.69	2113447 89.27	78.08	47288, 6	89522 ,4	96077 87	8.00	1448. 00	39937. 28
5	DKI JAKARTA A	2014	50,01	106508 8137.67	2226593 98.25	78.39	48108	84279 ,6	96077 87	8.95	1348. 00	41269. 03
5	DKI JAKARTA A	2015	-195,72	120834 7575.84	2604166 41.32	78.99	46355, 3	70899 ,3	96077 87	3.30	1359. 54	41328. 60
5	DKI JAKARTA A	2016	110,02	131338 5627.11	2889816 65.15	79.60	45993, 2	71070 ,8	96077 87	2.37	1359. 54	41328. 60
5	DKI JAKARTA A	2017	109,41	143726 1814.83	3068597 49.57	80.06	51,675, 9	81310 ,5	96077 87	3.72	6095. 82	31643. 13
5	DKI JAKARTA A	2018	55,6	157196 4454.61	3544714 21.51	80.47	54483, 9	93573 ,4	96077 87	3.27	4183. 74	32779. 19
5	DKI	2019	9,63	171914	3609770	80.76	54044,	88077	96077	3.27	3504.	34107.

	JAKART A			3962.44	58.91		4	,8	87		30	88
5	DKI JAKART A	2020	0	172600 5834.07	4131637 67.16	80.77	53655, 1	71751 ,4	96077 87	3.27	3504. 30	34107. 88
5	JAWA BARAT	2010	0	609626 574.67	5492208 1.00	66.15	941,5	3108, 2	43053 732	4.53	3217. 80	34053. 60
5	JAWA BARAT	2011	247	671158 666.78	5978692 7.33	66.67	1012,5	5620, 4	43053 732	2.75	3217. 80	34053. 60
5	JAWA BARAT	2012	137,41	734272 453.27	6899415 7.99	67.32	674,1	6168, 2	43053 732	4.02	4013. 05	36655. 28
5	JAWA BARAT	2013	102,41	812568 323.76	7371754 4.96	68.25	442,7	5897, 7	43053 732	7.97	3998. 74	39092. 56
5	JAWA BARAT	2014	50,01	881109 398.50	8120269 2.40	68.80	851,8	5766, 6	43053 732	7.76	4076. 66	43096. 46
5	JAWA BARAT	2015	-195,72	983765 226.82	9829276 4.94	69.50	351	4905	43053 732	3.93	4077. 90	44071. 43
5	JAWA BARAT	2016	110,02	107552 2040.90	1006728 16.97	70.05	210,4	4714, 9	43053 732	2.93	4077. 90	44071. 43
5	JAWA BARAT	2017	109,41	116936 7387.39	1079395 00.30	70.69	207,1	6570, 4	43053 732	3.46	7272. 16	50791. 20
5	JAWA BARAT	2018	55,6	127827 8895.69	1129350 58.42	71.30	230,7	8050, 9	43053 732	3.76	9697. 06	52878. 86
5	JAWA BARAT	2019	9,63	138776 2269.96	1174489 44.50	72.03	207,7	6444, 3	43053 732	3.76	10273 .56	54480. 28
5	JAWA BARAT	2020	0	137890 4384.43	1186889 57.77	72.09	184,3	5043, 2	43053 732	3.76	10273 .56	54480. 28
6	JAWA TENGAH	2010	0	389637 550.12	4946750 4.64	66.08	3863,2	9618, 8	32382 657	7.11	6509. 12	15315. 89
6	JAWA TENGAH	2011	247	429912 439.03	5528298 0.32	66.64	4678,3	12998 ,1	32382 657	2.87	6509. 12	15315. 89
6	JAWA TENGAH	2012	137,41	474886 733.82	6158149 3.37	67.21	4637,1	13972 ,4	32382 657	4.85	5168. 49	16600. 42
6	JAWA TENGAH	2013	102,41	520380 304.38	6929978 2.96	68.02	5319,7	15735 ,8	32382 657	8.19	5153. 86	18205. 08
6	JAWA TENGAH	2014	50,01	570433 401.17	7555644 8.86	68.78	5626,9	15767 ,9	32382 657	8.53	5154. 85	19631. 46
6	JAWA TENGAH	2015	-195,72	620264 015.08	8522591 2.08	69.49	5369,8	10717	32382 657	2.56	5155. 26	20408. 19
6	JAWA TENGAH	2016	110,02	660988 585.60	8758914 7.24	69.98	5384,6	8769, 1	32382 657	2.32	5155. 26	20408. 19
6	JAWA TENGAH	2017	109,41	711586 510.45	9426155 9.47	70.52	5982,3	10457 ,3	32382 657	3.64	7096. 65	21057. 04
6	JAWA TENGAH	2018	55,6	764808 380.14	9871716 9.57	71.12	6579	14266 ,8	32382 657	2.76	7150. 68	23558. 02
6	JAWA TENGAH	2019	9,63	821948 116.89	1032095 17.34	71.73	6743,6	12355 ,5	32382 657	2.76	7162. 82	24750. 62
6	JAWA TENGAH	2020	0	822095 502.18	9835980 4.69	71.87	6455,7	8635, 6	32382 657	2.76	7162. 82	24750. 62
6	DI YOGYA KARTA	2010	0	384429 40.59	9847893. 44	75.37	2446,8	3108, 2	34574 91	7.38	0.32	1869.7 7
6	DI YOGYA KARTA	2011	247	440295 82.93	1103964 9.77	75.93	3500,5	5620, 4	34574 91	3.88	0.32	1869.7 7
6	DI YOGYA KARTA	2012	137,41	494034 00.71	1198294 9.65	76.15	3954,2	6168, 2	34574 91	4.31	0.32	2043.7 5
6	DI YOGYA	2013	102,41	571018 87.22	1362983 3.88	76.44	3690	5897, 7	34574 91	7.32	0.32	2205.7 9

	KARTA											
6	DI YOGYA KARTA	2014	50,01	628751 41.17	1534742 8.32	76.81	5299,8	5766, 6	34574 91	6.59	0.32	2369.6 0
6	DI YOGYA KARTA	2015	-195,72	687305 27.54	1721415 4.28	77.59	4776,6	4905	34574 91	3.09	0.18	2484.1 6
6	DI YOGYA KARTA	2016	110,02	744297 95.62	1832176 1.49	78.38	6005,7	4714, 9	34574 91	2.29	0.18	2484.1 6
6	DI YOGYA KARTA	2017	109,41	813358 09.99	1950807 1.64	78.89	5003,4	6570, 4	34574 91	4.20	-	2724.4 9
6	DI YOGYA KARTA	2018	55,6	867531 96.83	2138211 3.04	79.53	4567,7	8050, 9	34574 91	2.66	-	2856.9 5
6	DI YOGYA KARTA	2019	9,63	924360 88.69	2243445 3.68	79.99	4522,8	6444, 3	34574 91	2.66	-	2856.9 5
6	DI YOGYA KARTA	2020	0	927535 41.94	2288920 6.61	79.97	3095,1	5043, 2	34574 91	2.66	-	2856.9 5
7	JAWA TIMUR	2010	0	629630 362.60	5976515 1.65	65.36	14209, 8	12 475,2	37476 757	7.33	9620. 62	24018. 69
7	JAWA TIMUR	2011	247	703343 083.11	7053090 6.42	66.06	16964, 4	15 721,7	37476 757	4.72	9620. 62	24018. 69
7	JAWA TIMUR	2012	137,41	781591 548.57	8619497 2.19	66.74	13557, 2	16 430,7	37476 757	4.39	11595 .42	26910. 18
7	JAWA TIMUR	2013	102,41	866916 172.60	9323247 4.47	67.55	12761, 5	17 463,6	37476 757	7.52	11547 .76	28708. 11
7	JAWA TIMUR	2014	50,01	949343 437.70	9694424 4.35	68.14	14528, 7	17 449,7	37476 757	7.90	14668 .05	30523. 98
7	JAWA TIMUR	2015	-195,72	101962 2140.96	1049123 33.83	68.95	13156, 4	13 841,2	37476 757	3.43	13504 .40	30824. 81
7	JAWA TIMUR	2016	110,02	110901 4191.23	1005369 19.26	69.74	13994, 1	13 593,1	37476 757	3.22	13504 .40	30824. 81
7	JAWA TIMUR	2017	109,41	119391 5047.01	1094440 01.07	70.27	15737, 7	15 472,2	37476 757	4.37	8199. 50	34114. 16
7	JAWA TIMUR	2018	55,6	129839 0491.77	1209910 67.09	70.77	16985, 6	17 652,6	37476 757	3.03	9396. 50	35817. 90
7	JAWA TIMUR	2019	9,63	139660 4489.98	1310039 36.27	71.50	16536, 8	16 545,7	37476 757	3.03	11072 .58	37228. 94
7	JAWA TIMUR	2020	0	139851 6772.62	1298868 60.99	71.71	16618, 7	14 546,3	37476 757	3.03	11072 .58	37228. 94
7	BALI	2010	0	530598 00.33	1094978 9.04	70.10	373,4	949,1	38907 57	8.10	3.84	3223.9 4
7	BALI	2011	247	597132 01.51	1277267 4.64	70.87	376,03 3	1 056,5	38907 57	3.75	3.84	3223.9 4
7	BALI	2012	137,41	658128 87.91	1464313 2.46	71.62	347,36 7	191,2	38907 57	4.71	453.8 7	3546.6 0
7	BALI	2013	102,41	696516 81.90	1661192 5.76	72.09	327,57	281,9	38907 57	7.35	454.0 2	3914.3 2
7	BALI	2014	50,01	764680 24.97	1598579 1.10	72.48	297,26 7	306,0	38907 57	8.03	441.8 9	4335.0 3
7	BALI	2015	-195,72	859109 54.33	1775067 9.10	73.27	745,13	140,8	38907 57	2.70	1017. 19	4594.1 8
7	BALI	2016	110,02	954976 86.01	1997780 6.53	73.65	783,87	173,1	38907 57	2.94	1017. 19	4594.1 8
7	BALI	2017	109,41	102152 931.82	2260358 3.30	74.30	646,2	136,0	38907 57	3.31	911.3 9	5069.6 4

7	BALI	2018	55,6	111762 439.69	2453144 3.84	74.77	457,1	314,1	38907 57	3.40	786.8 4	5247.1 6
7	BALI	2019	9,63	121140 031.51	2671760 3.75	75.38	407,03	261,1	38907 57	3.40	1041. 52	5706.7 3
7	BALI	2020	0	119957 693.75	2806899 8.65	75.50	327,57	123,3	38907 57	3.40	1041. 52	5706.7 3
7	NUSA TENGG RA BARAT	2010	0	425023 75.08	9183330. 60	61.16	1995,5	318,2	45002 12	11.07	146.0 0	837.17
7	NUSA TENGG RA BARAT	2011	247	473215 74.78	1039952 6.98	62.14	1136,9 3	328,9	45002 12	6.38	146.0 0	837.17
7	NUSA TENGG RA BARAT	2012	137,41	528157 32.96	1116051 6.74	62.98	596,67	283,7	45002 12	4.10	172.7 0	976.39
7	NUSA TENGG RA BARAT	2013	102,41	566434 75.61	1165870 8.80	63.76	400,86 7	314,0	45002 12	9.27	170.0 4	1133.3 3
7	NUSA TENGG RA BARAT	2014	50,01	620180 51.91	1538760 6.46	64.31	307,97	1 158,7	45002 12	7.18	445.3 9	1291.4 7
7	NUSA TENGG RA BARAT	2015	-195,72	660215 00.37	1686232 9.01	65.19	491,13	145,3	45002 12	3.25	393.8 0	1402.3 0
7	NUSA TENGG RA BARAT	2016	110,02	706782 00.51	1776690 2.48	65.81	525,17	111,6	45002 12	2.47	393.8 0	1402.3 0
7	NUSA TENGG RA BARAT	2017	109,41	748542 29.77	1921841 4.15	66.58	366,7	81,7	45002 12	3.59	418.4 9	1677.5 4
7	NUSA TENGG RA BARAT	2018	55,6	791130 27.33	1975721 9.46	67.30	157,8	161,3	45002 12	3.15	624.9 3	1776.8 1
7	NUSA TENGG RA BARAT	2019	9,63	839156 58.79	2023884 0.55	68.14	64,83	180,7	45002 12	3.15	795.7 5	1950.2 5
7	NUSA TENGG RA BARAT	2020	0	820512 99.10	2075826 8.34	68.25	197,07	193,9	45002 12	3.15	795.7 5	1950.2 5
7	NUSA TENGG RA TIMUR	2010	0	338947 67.77	1197959 0.90	59.21	34,1	36,4	46838 27	9.97	145.7 5	486.91
7	NUSA TENGG RA TIMUR	2011	247	383632 67.80	1393497 0.82	60.24	26,33	34,1	46838 27	4.32	145.7 5	486.91
7	NUSA TENGG RA	2012	137,41	426399 21.72	1595853 4.47	60.81	44,067	61,4	46838 27	5.10	158.6 9	567.32

	TIMUR											
7	NUSA TENGGA RA TIMUR	2013	102,41	473420 68.61	1708300 5.23	61.68	20,867	161,1	46838 27	8.84	160.5 4	639.57
7	NUSA TENGGA RA TIMUR	2014	50,01	506924 65.46	1948612 2.13	62.26	21,67	63,12	46838 27	8.32	272.8 0	702.26
7	NUSA TENGGA RA TIMUR	2015	-195,72	568514 66.36	2209109 2.85	62.67	515,13	20,7	46838 27	5.07	297.2 5	749.76
7	NUSA TENGGA RA TIMUR	2016	110,02	615063 12.16	2399470 6.03	63.13	558,27	63	46838 27	2.31	297.2 5	749.76
7	NUSA TENGGA RA TIMUR	2017	109,41	667075 42.95	2575433 1.57	63.73	389,3	54,2	46838 27	2.05	302.6 9	855.25
7	NUSA TENGGA RA TIMUR	2018	55,6	712544 39.23	2909850 7.51	64.39	167,6	171,1	46838 27	3.23	331.2 1	927.41
7	NUSA TENGGA RA TIMUR	2019	9,63	768913 65.23	2984527 0.42	65.23	81,03	76,1	46838 27	3.23	333.4 2	999.49
7	NUSA TENGGA RA TIMUR	2020	0	746266 26.07	2754284 6.60	65.19	212,87	58,5	46838 27	3.23	333.4 2	999.49
8	KALIMA NTAN BARAT	2010	0	479040 67.54	1091205 7.82	61.97	580,9	131,1	43959 83	8.52	230.5 1	1434.7 2
8	KALIMA NTAN BARAT	2011	247	536802 14.16	1227803 9.14	62.35	1260,8	207,6	43959 83	4.91	230.5 1	1434.7 2
8	KALIMA NTAN BARAT	2012	137,41	599236 83.53	1275023 6.72	63.41	964,1	470,2	43959 83	6.62	239.5 5	1603.7 2
8	KALIMA NTAN BARAT	2013	102,41	674124 98.73	1464832 2.59	64.30	893,5	404,5	43959 83	9.48	243.0 3	1889.3 9
8	KALIMA NTAN BARAT	2014	50,01	743260 99.85	1708008 6.16	64.89	596,5	428,7	43959 83	9.38	508.0 9	1862.4 4
8	KALIMA NTAN BARAT	2015	-195,72	809342 25.86	1930934 4.49	65.59	495,8	267,0	43959 83	6.17	653.4 9	1989.6 3
8	KALIMA NTAN BARAT	2016	110,02	889061 69.78	1899842 3.90	65.88	459	255,7	43959 83	3.88	653.4 9	1989.6 3
8	KALIMA NTAN BARAT	2017	109,41	968029 75.14	2059375 9.26	66.26	431,3	222,0	43959 83	3.86	603.4 9	2252.0 6
8	KALIMA NTAN BARAT	2018	55,6	102938 461.37	2230617 9.83	66.98	367,5	281,0	43959 83	3.99	778.8 2	2373.1 2

8	KALIMANTAN BARAT	2019	9,63	110748 437.24	2486788 5.32	67.65	413,5	107,5	43959 83	3.99	804.9 2	2572.6 9
8	KALIMANTAN BARAT	2020	0	110572 713.95	2610449 4.27	67.66	572,8	101,2	43959 83	3.99	804.9 2	2572.6 9
9	KALIMANTAN TENGAH	2010	0	255626 03.09	8217457. 86	65.96	3659,7	868,5	22120 89	9.49	89.05	649.95
9	KALIMANTAN TENGAH	2011	247	284862 03.75	9411470. 39	66.38	5715,5	1 238,5	22120 89	5.28	89.05	649.95
9	KALIMANTAN TENGAH	2012	137,41	316708 44.20	1076162 2.42	66.66	5204,6	1 233,6	22120 89	6.73	79.01	752.34
9	KALIMANTAN TENGAH	2013	102,41	346189 09.41	1190757 6.72	67.41	5654,7	1 328,8	22120 89	6.45	76.00	854.78
9	KALIMANTAN TENGAH	2014	50,01	380299 99.71	1351315 8.06	67.77	4493,8	1 192,6	22120 89	6.63	76.00	970.16
9	KALIMANTAN TENGAH	2015	-195,72	424186 17.95	1574445 7.12	68.53	8144,9	1 712,0	22120 89	4.20	242.1 5	1048.6 4
9	KALIMANTAN TENGAH	2016	110,02	473573 48.11	1621863 2.57	69.13	7668,7	992,4	22120 89	1.91	242.1 5	1048.6 4
9	KALIMANTAN TENGAH	2017	109,41	521838 60.42	1728385 6.20	69.79	10928, 2	1 199,2	22120 89	3.11	356.7 6	1134.9 5
9	KALIMANTAN TENGAH	2018	55,6	563158 79.35	1873811 6.92	70.42	11564, 5	2 142,8	22120 89	3.68	485.4 8	1223.7 9
9	KALIMANTAN TENGAH	2019	9,63	619202 06.68	1992703 8.58	70.91	10499, 2	1 641,7	22120 89	3.68	256.5 1	1358.7 7
9	KALIMANTAN TENGAH	2020	0	641261 31.26	2175473 5.17	71.05	8697,3	1 237,3	22120 89	3.68	256.5 1	1358.7 7
10	KALIMANTAN SELATAN	2010	0	407778 14.72	1065786 2.63	65.20	6339,7	1 419,4	36266 16	9.06	306.8 2	1467.1 3
10	KALIMANTAN SELATAN	2011	247	449950 01.57	1162659 5.46	65.89	9617	2 593,7	36266 16	3.98	306.8 2	1467.1 3
10	KALIMANTAN SELATAN	2012	137,41	488328 98.72	1354140 2.39	66.68	9476,5	2 752,7	36266 16	5.96	468.9 2	1688.4 4
10	KALIMANTAN SELATAN	2013	102,41	529982 41.86	1498123 4.14	67.17	8481,7	2 478,1	36266 16	6.98	478.3 2	1880.6 6
10	KALIMANTAN SELATAN	2014	50,01	585745 81.04	1603065 4.93	67.63	7931,2	2 127,9	36266 16	7.16	645.4 1	2092.2 3
10	KALIMANTAN	2015	-195,72	639420	1823051	68.38	35644,	1	36266	5.03	1671.	2187.6

	NTAN SELATAN			93.65	8.16		4	071,1	16		13	4
10	KALIMANTAN SELATAN	2016	110,02	690965 97.17	1909431 8.98	69.05	3327,2	698,2	36266 16	3.68	1671. 13	2187.6 4
10	KALIMANTAN SELATAN	2017	109,41	745549 61.35	1975896 7.90	69.65	4373,3	1 141,9	36266 16	3.82	1831. 94	2391.8 7
10	KALIMANTAN SELATAN	2018	55,6	804674 94.75	2124856 1.97	70.17	5054,2	1 143,7	36266 16	2.63	2790. 84	2602.3 9
10	KALIMANTAN SELATAN	2019	9,63	869606 66.27	2216264 9.33	70.72	4693,4	1 042,4	36266 16	2.63	3050. 81	2819.1 6
10	KALIMANTAN SELATAN	2020	0	876130 70.43	2194671 1.15	70.91	3293,5	485,6	36266 16	2.63	3050. 81	2819.1 6
10	KALIMANTAN TIMUR	2010	0	510590 96.90	1401398 9.57	71.31	21823	5 863,5	35531 43	7.00	381.2 8	2277.2 2
10	KALIMANTAN TIMUR	2011	247	575273 77.45	1510873 3.82	72.02	33030, 8	6 828,2	35531 43	6.23	381.2 8	2277.2 2
10	KALIMANTAN TIMUR	2012	137,41	654933 70.52	1734281 3.74	72.62	28747	7 801,2	35531 43	4.81	424.8 8	2502.3 2
10	KALIMANTAN TIMUR	2013	102,41	733964 21.73	2028161 5.33	73.21	26109, 5	8 765,9	35531 43	10.37	518.5 0	2731.5 8
10	KALIMANTAN TIMUR	2014	50,01	801802 86.67	2352317 4.00	73.82	21475, 2	7 791,3	35531 43	6.74	977.5 6	2815.5 5
10	KALIMANTAN TIMUR	2015	-195,72	867862 23.85	2594971 5.17	74.17	12546	4 567,8	35531 43	4.24	1053. 03	3007.3 0
10	KALIMANTAN TIMUR	2016	110,02	915368 46.47	2357834 3.61	74.59	9175,5	3 125,5	35531 43	2.83	1053. 03	3007.3 0
10	KALIMANTAN TIMUR	2017	109,41	968073 19.69	2159678 8.97	75.12	11349, 1	2 489,3	35531 43	3.69	1437. 95	3418.3 3
10	KALIMANTAN TIMUR	2018	55,6	102584 196.19	2376061 9.51	75.83	11576, 2	3 418,7	35531 43	3.32	1192. 23	3637.2 7
10	KALIMANTAN TIMUR	2019	9,63	109767 656.05	2629892 7.52	76.61	9941,9	1 555,8	35531 43	3.32	785.8 5	3952.8 8
10	KALIMANTAN TIMUR	2020	0	111183 751.56	2616382 8.57	76.24	8149,6	1 168,6	35531 43	3.32	785.8 5	3952.8 8
10	KALIMANTAN UTARA	2010	0	684835 2.68	3327520. 96	-	453,8	44,9	0	7.92	31.22	-
10	KALIMANTAN	2011	247	782714	3470878.	-	392	68,4	0	6.43	31.22	-

	NTAN UTARA			0.83	56							
10	KALIMA NTAN UTARA	2012	137,41	890955 0.86	4000676. 90	-	5204,6	70,0	0	5.99	31.22	-
10	KALIMA NTAN UTARA	2013	102,41	400067 6.90	5123223. 18	67.99	5654,7	93,7	0	10.35	31.22	180.73
10	KALIMA NTAN UTARA	2014	50,01	512322 3.18	6586508. 87	68.64	4493,8	33,0	0	11.91	84.82	199.37
10	KALIMA NTAN UTARA	2015	-195,72	122437 23.32	6884835. 73	68.76	8144,9	11,0	0	3.42	99.82	206.50
10	KALIMA NTAN UTARA	2016	110,02	130417 25.87	6722185. 09	69.20	7668,7	12,3	0	4.31	99.82	206.50
10	KALIMA NTAN UTARA	2017	109,41	137476 00.94	6184828. 23	69.84	10928, 2	15,3	0	2.77	73.60	180.59
10	KALIMA NTAN UTARA	2018	55,6	146080 34.44	6595911. 72	70.56	11564, 5	37,2	0	5.00	238.2 0	183.32
10	KALIMA NTAN UTARA	2019	9,63	160042 79.42	7184812. 63	71.15	10499, 2	20,2	0	5.00	238.2 0	264.55
10	KALIMA NTAN UTARA	2020	0	159975 55.15	7103647. 47	70.63	8697,3	46,9	0	5.00	238.2 0	264.55
11	SULAWESI UTARA	2010	0	254251 97.31	8422590. 91	67.83	373,6	70,8	22705 96	6.28	202.0 6	986.62
11	SULAWESI UTARA	2011	247	280317 71.92	1007773 0.91	68.31	744	144,4	22705 96	0.67	202.0 6	986.62
11	SULAWESI UTARA	2012	137,41	309086 82.00	1111027 0.30	69.04	941,8	122,6	22705 96	6.04	458.3 2	1087.0 8
11	SULAWESI UTARA	2013	102,41	327813 03.72	1234980 4.59	69.49	665,4	106,5	22705 96	8.12	345.1 9	1192.5 2
11	SULAWESI UTARA	2014	50,01	365412 76.27	1401607 3.31	69.96	833,2	117,7	22705 96	9.67	350.4 5	1240.3 2
11	SULAWESI UTARA	2015	-195,72	418061 12.12	1626783 3.70	70.39	676,7	68,9	22705 96	5.56	358.0 3	1302.5 8
11	SULAWESI UTARA	2016	110,02	455682 17.29	1721916 4.56	71.05	693,4	122,1	22705 96	0.35	358.0 3	1302.5 8
11	SULAWESI UTARA	2017	109,41	493649 86.52	1903374 4.10	71.66	627,9	65,6	22705 96	2.44	580.7 7	1544.8 7
11	SULAWESI UTARA	2018	55,6	527400 64.07	2114653 7.13	72.20	520,3	98,5	22705 96	3.83	557.2 2	1676.8 9
11	SULAWESI UTARA	2019	9,63	577440 90.60	2218200 4.38	72.99	296,4	133,5	22705 96	3.83	295.5 0	1787.8 7
11	SULAWESI UTARA	2020	0	572726	2241689	72.93	320,6	87,7	22705	3.83	295.5	1787.8

	SI UTARA			30.53	4.57				96		0	7
11	GORONT ALO	2010	0	969120 1.35	3642768. 28	62.65	212,1	19,4	10401 64	7.43	33.20	236.52
11	GORONT ALO	2011	247	108946 75.25	4277192. 00	63.48	584	89,9	10401 64	4.08	33.20	236.52
11	GORONT ALO	2012	137,41	122290 32.64	4843216. 78	64.16	805,9	165,7	10401 64	5.31	31.44	293.13
11	GORONT ALO	2013	102,41	137177 87.55	5497584. 18	64.70	925,4	279,5	10401 64	5.84	31.44	328.40
11	GORONT ALO	2014	50,01	154039 67.17	6077544. 61	65.17	306,3	282,4	10401 64	6.14	64.73	366.08
11	GORONT ALO	2015	-195,72	174836 51.60	6809069. 25	65.86	1469,5	510,7	10401 64	4.30	31.49	398.82
11	GORONT ALO	2016	110,02	193003 21.72	7215175. 33	66.29	2345,3	603,9	10401 64	1.30	31.49	398.82
11	GORONT ALO	2017	109,41	212339 31.10	7804161. 78	67.01	3938,8	824,1	10401 64	4.34	56.83	460.13
11	GORONT ALO	2018	55,6	232342 74.80	8245792. 68	67.71	6480,5	294,9	10401 64	2.15	57.91	503.49
11	GORONT ALO	2019	9,63	254322 78.57	8725060. 00	68.49	7554,5	590,2	10401 64	2.15	57.41	543.84
11	GORONT ALO	2020	0	258603 13.11	8246397. 97	68.68	9986,5	343,2	10401 64	2.15	57.41	543.84
11	SULAWE SI TENGG RA	2010	0	254380 20.25	7712647. 84	65.99	461,9	19,4	22325 86	3.87	91.30	441.08
11	SULAWE SI TENGG RA	2011	247	282238 69.28	9683828. 69	66.52	758,4	89,9	22325 86	5.09	91.30	441.08
11	SULAWE SI TENGG RA	2012	137,41	323979 70.95	1003652 2.54	67.07	594,2	165,7	22325 86	5.25	125.2 4	528.42
11	SULAWE SI TENGG RA	2013	102,41	364892 59.48	1089720 3.38	67.55	409,2	279,5	22325 86	5.92	129.2 4	621.64
11	SULAWE SI TENGG RA	2014	50,01	403396 23.11	1171719 0.11	68.07	278,3	282,4	22325 86	7.40	233.0 7	670.71
11	SULAWE SI TENGG RA	2015	-195,72	440922 55.44	1310328 3.67	68.75	128,9	510,7	22325 86	1.64	127.4 7	703.59
11	SULAWE SI TENGG RA	2016	110,02	483165 52.74	1422009 3.00	69.31	107,1	603,9	22325 86	3.07	127.4 7	703.59
11	SULAWE SI TENGG RA	2017	109,41	532977 32.04	1589705 4.71	69.86	141	824,1	22325 86	2.96	296.5 9	850.70
11	SULAWE SI TENGG RA	2018	55,6	582670 74.66	1740378 4.03	70.61	286,1	1 294,9	22325 86	2.55	293.3 8	911.73

11	SULAWESI TENGGARA	2019	9,63	634664 17.86	1887897 6.19	71.20	319,1	1 590,2	22325 86	2.55	148.9 2	986.89
11	SULAWESI TENGGARA	2020	0	643906 63.53	1888797 5.66	71.45	119,4	1 343,2	22325 86	2.55	148.9 2	986.89
12	SULAWESI TENGAH	2010	0	315957 55.09	8009483. 78	63.29	320,4	11,8	26350 09	6.40	175.7 3	574.71
12	SULAWESI TENGAH	2011	247	349435 33.27	9169333. 77	64.27	147	11,9	26350 09	4.47	175.7 3	574.71
12	SULAWESI TENGAH	2012	137,41	392082 94.30	1042536 4.46	65.00	85,1	2,7	26350 09	5.87	189.1 8	686.19
12	SULAWESI TENGAH	2013	102,41	439876 10.28	1178390 6.76	65.79	38,1,8	15,5	26350 09	7.57	198.0 9	758.70
12	SULAWESI TENGAH	2014	50,01	505585 62.97	5055856 2.97	66.43	118,6	42,1	26350 09	8.85	422.4 1	865.77
12	SULAWESI TENGAH	2015	-195,72	558342 96.84	1536975 7.18	66.76	340,2	28,4	26350 09	4.17	421.1 2	948.78
12	SULAWESI TENGAH	2016	110,02	609610 78.61	1621069 1.37	67.47	364,4	9,4	26350 09	1.49	421.1 2	948.78
12	SULAWESI TENGAH	2017	109,41	664406 83.51	1754523 7.69	68.11	404,7	3,1	26350 09	4.33	490.6 2	1068.7 9
12	SULAWESI TENGAH	2018	55,6	729764 47.27	1793601 0.91	68.88	457,8	4,4	26350 09	6.46	1718. 47	1171.0 8
12	SULAWESI TENGAH	2019	9,63	794215 63.15	1979270 9.68	69.50	467,7	11,6	26350 09	6.46	1746. 21	1146.2 3
12	SULAWESI TENGAH	2020	0	776245 93.72	2008614 6.18	69.55	507,8	2,9	26350 09	6.46	1746. 21	1146.2 3
12	SULAWESI SELATAN	2010	0	996611 10.94	2057807 3.82	66.00	2312	955,6	80347 76	6.82	625.9 6	3246.4 2
12	SULAWESI SELATAN	2011	247	113547 230.59	2349133 7.09	66.65	1898,6	1 364,5	80347 76	2.87	625.9 6	3246.4 2
12	SULAWESI SELATAN	2012	137,41	129687 947.32	1296879 47.32	67.26	1516,6	1 180,8	80347 76	4.57	1045. 81	3639.6 3
12	SULAWESI SELATAN	2013	102,41	146643 073.88	2871894 0.13	67.92	1550,9	1 189,8	80347 76	6.24	1084. 85	4156.4 9
12	SULAWESI SELATAN	2014	50,01	165652 215.83	3177436 5.70	68.49	1736,1	813,6	80347 76	8.51	968.9 2	4339.2 2

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12	SULAWESI SELATAN	2015	-195,72	185585 543.03	3639661 5.59	69.15	568,4	612,1	80347 76	5.18	1232. 35	4479.4 6
12	SULAWESI SELATAN	2016	110,02	204368 749.91	3739919 1.96	69.76	513,6	665,4	80347 76	3.18	1232. 35	4479.4 6
12	SULAWESI SELATAN	2017	109,41	225404 554.58	3939317 2.37	70.34	265,1	8 328,6	80347 76	4.48	1450. 85	5172.5 0
12	SULAWESI SELATAN	2018	55,6	251147 504.70	4482750 7.85	70.90	395,8	1 013,3	80347 76	3.48	2953. 94	5472.4 8
12	SULAWESI SELATAN	2019	9,63	274463 638.68	4942929 3.61	71.66	828,2	977,6	80347 76	3.48	2995. 60	5945.5 6
12	SULAWESI SELATAN	2020	0	278594 012.06	4863367 9.90	71.93	818,6	747,6	80347 76	3.48	2995. 60	5945.5 6
12	SULAWESI BARAT	2010	0	104535 66.60	3192723. 39	59.74	24	19,4	11586 51	5.12	6.49	151.52
12	SULAWESI BARAT	2011	247	117338 46.66	3732160. 42	60.63	2,7	89,9	11586 51	4.91	6.49	151.52
12	SULAWESI BARAT	2012	137,41	127266 92.87	4267713. 89	61.01	0	165,7	11586 51	3.28	6.39	177.63
12	SULAWESI BARAT	2013	102,41	140144 32.23	4694733. 05	61.53	0	279,5	11586 51	5.91	12.39	207.59
12	SULAWESI BARAT	2014	50,01	152616 35.11	5153208. 58	62.24	152	282,4	11586 51	7.88	11.68	238.03
12	SULAWESI BARAT	2015	-195,72	172190 20.72	6026226. 40	62.96	0	510,7	11586 51	5.07	3.22	258.70
12	SULAWESI BARAT	2016	110,02	188839 77.76	6781949. 00	63.60	0	603,9	11586 51	2.23	3.22	258.70
12	SULAWESI BARAT	2017	109,41	203888 14.62	7342269. 61	64.30	0,2	824,1	11586 51	3.79	3.22	312.89
12	SULAWESI BARAT	2018	55,6	221463 97.19	7902508. 45	65.10	0	1 294,9	11586 51	1.80	63.22	345.28
12	SULAWESI BARAT	2019	9,63	232618 40.60	8087420. 28	65.73	1,4	590,2	11586 51	1.80	67.77	380.08
12	SULAWESI BARAT	2020	0	241901 33.25	7371770. 45	66.11	2,1	1 343,2	11586 51	1.80	67.77	380.08
13	MALUKU	2010	0	125028 64.76	7126877. 38	64.27	165,3	336,3	15335 06	8.78	134.6 5	336.69

13	MALUK U	2011	247	138127 54.73	9245920. 57	64.75	195	361,2	15335 06	2.85	134.6 5	336.69
13	MALUK U	2012	137,41	162304 82.46	1623048 2.46	65.43	243,8	429,1	15335 06	6.73	135.0 6	397.49
13	MALUK U	2013	102,41	181672 97.01	1083119 2.56	66.09	209,4	357,9	15335 06	8.81	147.6 1	469.96
13	MALUK U	2014	50,01	212262 34.07	1182558 7.55	66.74	152,2	392,1	15335 06	6.81	211.7 9	480.08
13	MALUK U	2015	-195,72	240484 12.34	1377500 0.51	67.05	42,8	297,4	15335 06	5.92	236.7 6	509.51
13	MALUK U	2016	110,02	266462 84.39	1490071 2.08	67.60	121,1	307,1	15335 06	3.28	236.7 6	509.51
13	MALUK U	2017	109,41	286566 69.59	1563808 9.97	68.19	95,8	495,2	15335 06	-0.05	263.3 7	463.05
13	MALUK U	2018	55,6	300965 78.75	3009657 8.75	68.87	192,7	642,7	15335 06	3.53	297.0 6	597.37
13	MALUK U	2019	9,63	327535 25.98	1645658 5.84	69.45	245,2	515,8	15335 06	3.53	363.4 3	519.13
13	MALUK U	2020	0	330082 12.31	1673823 6.08	69.49	186,3	503,9	15335 06	3.53	363.4 3	519.13
13	MALUK UTARA	2010	0	963826 8.05	4215399. 12	62.79	309,9	24,0	10380 87	5.32	62.04	204.67
13	MALUK UTARA	2011	247	105669 33.36	5184808. 38	63.19	547,3	20,3	10380 87	4.52	62.04	204.67
13	MALUK UTARA	2012	137,41	115460 49.48	6022774. 64	63.93	446	5,3	10380 87	3.29	44.60	235.88
13	MALUK UTARA	2013	102,41	127488 37.48	6903319. 10	64.78	645	3,2	10380 87	9.78	49.60	259.10
13	MALUK UTARA	2014	50,01	139571 49.41	7965612. 06	65.18	52,4	5,1	10380 87	9.34	65.70	309.37
13	MALUK UTARA	2015	-195,72	154645 67.77	8856577. 32	65.91	40	40,8	10380 87	4.52	73.81	329.44
13	MALUK UTARA	2016	110,02	169432 43.12	9222776. 71	66.63	36,1	102,9	10380 87	1.91	73.81	329.44
13	MALUK UTARA	2017	109,41	183596 22.74	9893536. 19	67.20	101,1	100,9	10380 87	1.97	124.3 8	237.12
13	MALUK UTARA	2018	55,6	199966 17.07	1999661 7.07	67.76	194,5	156,5	10380 87	4.12	88.36	401.48
13	MALUK UTARA	2019	9,63	214000 16.62	1215856 5.81	68.70	245	355,2	10380 87	4.12	120.2 7	537.52
13	MALUK UTARA	2020	0	216971 52.93	1166883 4.91	68.49	286,7	404,6	10380 87	4.12	120.2 7	537.52
13	PAPUA BARAT	2010	0	109066 86.08	6781745. 40	59.60	1690,8	70,7	76042 2	4.68	55.67	305.08
13	PAPUA BARAT	2011	247	115072 09.97	7792314. 61	59.90	3027,2	60,6	76042 2	3.64	55.67	305.08
13	PAPUA BARAT	2012	137,41	122996 50.83	9037898. 58	60.30	3652	19,5	76042 2	4.88	58.67	346.65
13	PAPUA	2013	102,41	133757	1029620	60.91	3518,3	33,5	76042	4.63	66.64	383.99

	BARAT			61.35	1.40				2			
13	PAPUA BARAT	2014	50,01	147169 98.61	1159472 3.56	61.28	3894	32,6	76042 2	5.70	102.8 0	430.63
13	PAPUA BARAT	2015	-195,72	165733 09.27	1298266 2.64	61.73	2768,1	71,6	76042 2	2.77	112.7 6	455.58
13	PAPUA BARAT	2016	110,02	185490 37.83	1438311 1.84	62.21	1852,3	105,4	76042 2	5.75	112.7 6	455.58
13	PAPUA BARAT	2017	109,41	204836 26.43	1489373 6.70	62.99	2050,6	107,8	76042 2	1.78	403.5 9	533.47
13	PAPUA BARAT	2018	55,6	225132 51.69	1541356 1.42	63.74	2986,6	193,5	76042 2	6.02	121.0 9	569.02
13	PAPUA BARAT	2019	9,63	245980 65.60	1725606 2.45	64.70	2537,6	399,8	76042 2	6.02	147.9 2	510.01
13	PAPUA BARAT	2020	0	246811 38.44	1670452 9.27	65.09	2040,7	421,7	76042 2	6.02	147.9 2	510.01
13	PAPUA	2010	0	392523 06.16	1818954 3.25	54.45	5042	945,7	28333 81	4.48	91.64	522.80
13	PAPUA	2011	247	448104 10.89	2035144 9.70	55.01	3664,3	119,5	28333 81	3.40	91.64	522.80
13	PAPUA	2012	137,41	501648 29.26	2273479 9.38	55.55	2146,3	025,7	28333 81	4.52	96.25	600.67
13	PAPUA	2013	102,41	573239 63.55	2617623 5.14	56.25	2747,7	507,1	28333 81	8.27	106.3 0	713.26
13	PAPUA	2014	50,01	653937 61.18	3045700 8.67	56.75	1493,2	016,2	28333 81	7.98	242.4 4	724.78
13	PAPUA	2015	-195,72	716992 11.76	3406965 4.56	57.25	1940,7	693,8	28333 81	2.79	271.1 4	763.32
13	PAPUA	2016	110,02	800622 32.52	3623889 6.82	58.05	1988,9	716,9	28333 81	4.13	271.1 4	763.32
13	PAPUA	2017	109,41	879035 33.79	3881054 3.43	59.09	2489	362,0	28333 81	2.41	128.1 9	868.01
13	PAPUA	2018	55,6	981103 17.91	4085961 5.11	60.06	4003,1	398,4	28333 81	6.70	550.0 2	916.96
13	PAPUA	2019	9,63	105361 803.20	4389819 2.85	60.84	1384,4	486,4	28333 81	6.70	580.6 4	1057.6 5
13	PAPUA	2020	0	101038 245.83	4410035 8.32	60.44	2128,7	475,5	28333 81	6.70	580.6 4	1057.6 5
14	34 PROVIN SI	2010	0	378577 4662.09	6181779 92.00	66.53	157779 ,1	135 663,3	23764 1326	6.96	35596 .74	15869 4.89
14	34 PROVIN SI	2011	247	422461 8838.30	7095015 33.02	67.09	203496 ,6	177 435,6	23764 1326	3.79	35596 .74	15869 4.89
14	34 PROVIN SI	2012	137,41	471167 3963.82	8075045 05.19	67.70	190020 ,3	191 689,5	23764 1326	4.30	44841 .54	17434 1.92
14	34 PROVIN SI	2013	102,41	527028 6756.16	9040465 57.38	68.31	182,55 1,8	186 628,7	23764 1326	8.38	45476 .31	18834 2.41
14	34 PROVIN SI	2014	50,01	583030 8768.94	9803422 35.59	68.90	175980	178 178,8	23764 1326	8.36	53015 .70	19902 8.08
14	34 PROVIN SI	2015	-195,72	642999 9703.23	1113773 453.19	69.55	150366 ,3	142 694,8	23764 1326	3.35	54624 .17	20427 9.97
14	34 PROVIN SI	2016	110,02	698819 5176.70	1166886 102.93	70.18	145134	135 652,8	23764 1326	3.02	54624 .17	20427 9.97
14	34 PROVIN	2017	109,41	757977 9032.04	1248350 823.73	70.81	168828 ,2	156 985,5	23764 1326	3.61	58647 .49	22601 4.06

	SI											
14	34 PROVIN SI	2018	55,6	823573 9335.27	1364688 111.84	71.39	180012 ,7	188 711,3	23764 1326	3.13	63946 .60	23901 2.04
14	34 PROVIN SI	2019	9,63	891089 2062.96	1438889 391.65	71.92	167683	171 275,7	23764 1326	3.13	66607 .83	24765 3.33
14	34 PROVIN SI	2020	0	890575 6851.84	1475387 803.30	71.94	163191 ,8	141 568,8	23764 1326	3.13	66607 .83	24765 3.33
		2010 - 2020	-195,72	378577 4662.09	6181779 92.00	66,53- 71,94	>145< 203	135- 191	23764 1326	>10, >5, <0		15869 4.89
			247	890575 6851.84	1475387 803.30		4,2647 05882	3,970 58823 5	69894 50,76 5		1029, 41176 5	24765 3.33
			<0	108823 529	1818170 5,65		5,9705 88235	5,617 64705 9			1941, 17647 1	4667,4 70588
			<100	261764 705,9	4339375 8,91	66-72	4.000- 6.000	4.000 - 6.000	7.000. 000		1000- 2000	7283,3 23529
			>00,01	100000 000- 300000 000	18.000.0 00- 44.000.0 00							4500- 7250

Source: Authors Analysis, 2022

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

There are 6 cluster of region (sub island / islands) categorized as developed areas, while the other 7 classified as developing areas, and none of them is poverty areas.

➤ They are :

- *Developed Areas (Inflations Minimum Once in 10 Years more than 10 %):*

Cluster 1 (Aceh – Sumatera Utara); cluster 2 (Sumatera Barat - Riau – Kepulauan Riau); cluster 3 (Jambi – Sumatera Selatan – Bengkulu – Kepulauan Bangka Belitung); cluster 4 (Lampung – Banten); cluster 7 (Jawa Timur – Bali – Nusa Tenggara Barat – Nusa Tenggara Timur); dan cluster 10 (Kalimantan Selatan – Kalimantan Timur- Kalimantan Utara);

- *Developing Areas (Inflations Minimum Once in 10 Years Less than 10 %):*

Cluster 5 (DKI Jarta – Jawa Barat); cluster 6 (Jawa Tengah – DIY); cluster 8-9 (Kalimantan Barat – Kalimantan Tengah); cluster 11 (Sulawesi Utara- Gorontalo- Sulawesi Tenggara); cluster 12 (Sulawesi Tengah – Sulawesi Selatan – Sulawesi Barat); dan cluster 13 (Maluku- Maluku Utara- Papua Barat-Papua);

- *Poverty Areas (Inflations Minimum Once in 10 Years more than 5 %):*

None of 13 cclusters.

➤ *The Attainment of Carbon Emission Targets During 2010-2020 are Assumed Impacted of the Spaces Both Public and Privates*

- Carbon emission : <0 %,0,01-100 %, and > 100,01 %;
- Household Consumption : 100.000.000-300.000.000;
- Government Spending : 188.000.000-44.000.000;
- IPM : 66 % - 72 %;
- Expor : 4.000-6.000;
- Impor : 4.000-6.000;
- Penduduk : >7.000.000;
- Inflation : <0, >5, >10;
- Towers : 1.000-2.000;
- Networks : 4.500 – 7.250.

➤ *The Enlargement and Reducing Stock of Spaces are Proposed by the Achievement of Green Shading (Upper Mean) or Yellow Shading (below in between bottom and too mean) and Pink Shading (below mean).*

- Level of wealth in **green zone** at Sumatera Utara, Banten, DKI Jakarta, Jawa Tengah, Jawa Timur; **yellow zone** at Aceh, Sumatera Barat, Riau, Kepulauan Riau, Sumatera Selatan, Lampung, Jawa Barat, Bali, Kalimantan Barat, Kalimantan Timur ; and **pink zone** at Jambi, Bengkulu, Kepulauan Bangka Belitung, DIY, Nusa Tenggara Barat, Nusa Tenggara Timur, Kalimantan Tengah, Kalimantan Selatan, Kalimantan Utara, Sulawesi Utara, Gorontalo, Sulawesi Tenggara, Sulawesi Tengah, Sulawesi Selatan, Sulawesi Barat, Maluku, Maluku Utara, Papua Barat, dan Papua.

- Government Spending in **green zone** in Sumatera Utara, DKI Jakarta, Jawa Barat, Jawa Tengah, Jawa Timur, Sulawesi Selatan, Maluku Utara, dan Papua ; **yellow zones** in Aceh, Sumatera Barat, Riau, Sumatera Selatan, Lampung, DIY, Bali , Nusa Tenggara Timur, Nusa Tenggara Barat, Kalimantan Barat, Kalimantan Tengah, Kalimantan Selatan, Kalimantan Timur, Sulawesi Utara, Sulawesi Tenggara, Sulawesi Tengah and **pink zones** Kepulauan Riau, Jambi, Bengkulu, Kepulauan Bangka Belitung, Banten, Kalimantan Utara, Gorontalo, Sulawesi Barat, Maluku, Papua Barat,;
- *The Linkage between each Variables as so the Row of Columns can be Grouped as New Policies for each Provinces.*
- For Green zone : reduce the housing estates, education spaces, industrial and trade centres, and office complex, enlarge the spaces for recreational, forest and wet lands, public infrastructures, green public free and rent areas; and grey private open spaces;
 - For Yellow zone : maintain all area dan keep existance of the all function spaces;
 - For the pink zone : reverse back from the point a.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Central Stathysical Board, 2022.
- [2]. Ministry of Environment and Forestry. 2021. The Report of MRV 2020.